

Appendix 3:
A List of the Insect Fauna of Nantucket, Massachusetts
Selected Phytophagous and Parasitoid Groups, Revised from Johnson (1930)

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In the list that follows, the species listed by Johnson (1930) have been brought up to date with current taxonomy. Johnson's notes are presented in quotations, and the name listed by Johnson (if different) is indicated after the "Johnson 1930" citation. Taxa preceded by a "*" are new to the list. Depositories for new material are coded as follows:

ASJ = Private collection of Andrew Jensen, Eagle, ID

BG = BugGuide.net; to view image, add the number to the end of <http://bugguide.net/node/view/>

BMNH = Natural History Museum, London, UK

CM = Private collection of Chris Mallory, Long Beach, CA

CNC = Canadian National Collection of Insects, Ottawa, ON

CSE = Private collection of Charley Eiseman, Northfield, MA

CUIC = Cornell University Insect Collection, Ithaca, NY

EME = Essig Museum of Entomology, Berkeley, CA

INAT = iNaturalist.org; to view image, add the number to the end of
<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/>

INHS = Illinois Natural History Survey, Champaign, IL

MLBM = Monte L. Bean Life Science Museum, Brigham Young University, Provo, UT

MMA = Maria Mitchell Association, Nantucket, MA

ROM = Royal Ontario Museum, Toronto, ON

USNM = National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, DC

ZFMK = Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum Alexander Koenig, Bonn, Germany

CONTENTS

THYSANOPTERA (Thrips).....	3
HEMIPTERA (True Bugs, Cicadas, Hoppers, Aphids, etc.).....	3
Heteroptera (True Bugs)	3
Auchenorrhyncha (Free-living Hemipterans).....	5
Cercopoidea (Spittlebugs).....	5
Cicadoidea (Leafhoppers, Treehoppers).....	6
Fulgoroidea (Planthoppers).....	10
Sternorrhyncha (Plant-parasitic Hemipterans).....	11
Aphidoidea (Aphids).....	11
Coccoidea (Scale Insects)	12
Phylloxeroidea (Adelgids, Phylloxerans)	12
Psylloidea (Psyllids).....	13
COLEOPTERA (Beetles).....	13
Buprestoidea (Jewel Beetles, Metallic Wood-boring Beetles)	13
Chrysomeloidea (Long-horned Beetles, Leaf Beetles).....	14
Curculionoidea (Snout and Bark Beetles, Weevils)	22
HYMENOPTERA: Symphyta (Sawflies, Horntails).....	28
Cephoidea	28
Siricoidea	28
Tenthredinoidea	29
HYMENOPTERA: Parasitica (Parasitic Wasps).....	32
Diaprioidea.....	32
Chalcidoidea	32
LEPIDOPTERA (Moths and Butterflies).....	36
Gelechioidea (Twirler Moths etc).....	36
Yponomeutoidea (Ermine Moths etc).....	41
Tortricidae (Leafroller Moths).....	42
DIPTERA (Flies)	53
Tephritoidea (Fruit Flies, Lance Flies, Picture-winged Flies, Signal Flies)	53
Literature Cited	55

THYSANOPTERA (Thrips)

PHLAEOTHIRIPIDAE (Tube-tailed Thrips)

* *Haplothrips graminis* Hood, 1912. Collected on *Schoenoplectus pungens* at the UMass field station, 9/8/2019 (CNC; BG 1908788).

THRIPIDAE

* *Limothrips denticornis* (Haliday, 1836). Feeding under leaf sheaths of *Alopecurus pratensis* along Grove Lane, 6/15/2018 (CNC; BG 1911450).

HEMIPTERA (True Bugs, Cicadas, Hoppers, Aphids, etc.)

Heteroptera (True Bugs)

MIRIDAE (Plant Bugs) (Johnson 1930, p. 28)

Adelphocoris rapidus (Say, 1832). Rapid plant bug. “Common, July 20–Aug. 16. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930).

Blepharidopterus provancheri (Burque, 1887). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 7, 1929” (Johnson 1930, *Diaphnidia pellucida* Uhl.).

Calocoris norvegicus (Gmelin, 1790). Strawberry bug. “Common, The Creek and Grove Lane, June 23 and July 20” (Johnson 1930).

Capsus ater (Linnaeus, 1758). “Fair grounds, June 23. Hidden forest, July 27. Polpis, July 27” (Johnson 1930; incl. var. *semiflavus* and var. *tyrannus*).

Chlamydatus associatus (Uhler, 1872). Ragweed plant bug. “Aug. 22 (Fernald)” (Johnson 1930).

Collaria oculata (Reuter, 1876). “July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930).

Coquillettia mimetica Osborn, 1898. “July 11 (Morse), Surfside, July 25. Taupaushaw, Aug. 17 (Emerton)” (Johnson 1930).

Cyrtorhinus caricis (Fallén, 1807). “Aug. 6 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930, *C. caricis* Kngt.).

Hyaliodes vitripennis (Say, 1832). “Polpis, Aug. 6 and Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930).

Leptopterna dolabrata (Linnaeus, 1758). “Common, June 23–July 11” (Johnson 1930, *Miris dolabratus* Linn.).

Lopus decolor (Fallén, 1807). “Common, June 23–July 14” (Johnson 1930).

Lygocoris belfragii (Reuter, 1876). “Maxcys Pond, July 14” (Johnson 1930, *Lygus* (*Neolygus*) *belfragii* Reut.).

Lygocoris communis (Knight, 1916). Pear plant bug / green apple bug. “Madaket, July 16” (Johnson 1930, *Lygus* (*Neolygus*) *communis* Kngt.).

Lygocoris hirticulus (Van Duzee, 1916). “Polpis, Aug. 6” (Johnson 1930, *Lygus* (*Neolygus*) *hirticulus* VanD.).

Lygocoris pabulinus (Linnaeus, 1761). “July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930, *Lygus pabulinus* Linn.).

Lygus lineolaris (Palisot, 1818). Tarnished plant bug. “Common, July 20–Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930, *L. pratensis* L. var. *oblineatus* Say and var. *strigulatus* Walk.).

Lygus rubrosignatus Knight, 1923. “July 14–Aug. 9. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930, *L. pratensis* var. *rubrosignatus* Kngt.).

Neurocolpus nubilus (Say, 1832). Clouded plant bug. “Common, July 4–Aug. 18” (Johnson 1930).

Orectoderus obliquus Uhler, 1876. “July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930).

Phytocoris antennalis Reuter, 1909. “The Creeks, Aug. 21, 1926” (Johnson 1930).

Phytocoris eximius Reuter, 1876. “Polpis, Aug. 6 and Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930).

Phytocoris pallidicornis Reuter, 1876. “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17, Aug. 19. 1909 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930).

Pilophorus amoenus Uhler, 1887. “Fair grounds, Aug. 8, 1918” (Johnson 1930).

Pilophorus crassipes Heidemann, 1892. “Woods on road to Taupaushaw, on pine. Aug. 17 (Emerton). Surfside, Aug. 8, 1929” (Johnson 1930, *P. vanduzeei* Kngt.).

Pithanus maerkelii (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838). “Polpis, on grass, July 27” (Johnson 1930).

Plagiognathus chrysanthemi (Wolff, 1804). “Maxcys Pond, July 16, 1926” (Johnson 1930).

Plagiognathus longirostris (Knight, 1923). “Sacacha Pond, July 19” (Johnson 1930, *Microphylellus longirostris* Kngt.).

Plagiognathus morrisoni (Knight, 1923). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17, 1927” (Johnson 1930, *Psallus morrisoni* Kngt.).

Poecilocapsus lineatus (Fabricius, 1798). Four-lined plant bug. “Common, July 16–21” (Johnson 1930).

Polymerus basalis (Reuter, 1876). “Common, June 23–July 11” (Johnson 1930).

Porpomiris curtulus (Reuter, 1909). “On tall grass, Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930, *Mesomiris curtulus* Reut.).

Prepops circumcinctus (Say, 1832). “Taupaushaw, July 25–Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Platytylellus circumcinctus* Say).

* *Pseudoxenetes regalis* (Uhler, 1890). Eastern regal oak mirid. Found nymph in car after leaving Sconset Dump, 6/16/2018 (BG 1633799).

Rhinocapsus rubricans (Provancher, 1887). “Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19. 1926” (Johnson 1930).

Stenodema trispinosum Reuter, 1904. “June 24” (Johnson 1930, *Stenoderma trispinosum* Reut.).

Stenodema vicinum (Provancher, 1872). “Maxcys Pond, Aug. 18” (Johnson 1930, *Stenoderma vicinum* Prov.).

Taedia colon (Say, 1832). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17, 1927” (Johnson 1930, *Paracalocoris colon* Say).

Taylorilygus apicalis (Fieber, 1861). “Polpis, Aug. 6. Sacacha Pond, Aug. 16” (Johnson 1930, *Lygus apicalis* Fieb.).

Trigonotylus ruficornis (Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785). “July 4 (Cushman). July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930).

Trigonotylus uhleri (Reuter, 1876). “Polpis, July 27. The Creek marshes, July 21” (Johnson 1930).

Tytthus vagus (Knight, 1923). “Aug. 6 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930, *Cyrtorhinus vagus* Knegt.).

Auchenorrhyncha (Free-living Hemipterans)

(Johnson 1930, p. 32)

CERCOPOIDEA [=Cercopidae in Johnson 1930] (Spittlebugs)

APHROPHORIDAE

Aphrophora cribrata (Walker, F., 1851). Pine Spittlebug. 41.27795, -70.01008, 7/30/2017 (BG 1461990); “Common, Aug. 17–Sept. 8” (Johnson 1930, *Aphrophora parallela* Say).

Aphrophora quadrinotata Say, 1830. “July 11 (Morse). Aug. 16–Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930).

Aphrophora saratogensis Fitch, 1851. Dead Horse Valley, 8/6/2012 (BG 741537); “July 11 (Morse). Aug. 9–Sept. 14. On pine” (Johnson 1930).

Lepyronia quadrangularis (Say, 1825). “Polpis, Aug. 6” (Johnson 1930).

Neophilaenus lineatus (Linnaeus, 1758). “‘Grass Spittle Bug.’ Common. July 4–Sept. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Philaenus lineatus* Linn.).

Philaenarcys bilineata (Say, 1830). “July 4, July 11 (Morse). Sacacha Pond, Aug. 16” (Johnson 1930, *Philaronia bilineata* Say).

* *Philaenus spumarius* (Linnaeus, 1758). Meadow Spittlebug. Siasconset, 6/17/2017 (BG 1402844).

CERCOPIDAE

Prosapia ignipecta (Fitch, 1856). “Polpis, Aug. 6” (Johnson 1930, *Monecophora bicincta* var. *ignipecta* Fitch).

CLASTOPTERIDAE

Clastoptera hyperici McAtee, 1920. “July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930, *C. proteus* var. *hyperici* McAtee).

Clastoptera proteus Fitch, 1851. “July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930).

Clastoptera saintcyri Provancher, 1872. “Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930, *C. proteus* var. *saint-cyri* Prov.).

CICADOIDEA

CICADELLIDAE (Leafhoppers)

Aceratagallia sanguinolenta (Provancher, 1872). “May 10 (Brooks). Polpis, Aug. 5” (Johnson 1930, *Agallia sanguinolenta* Prov.).

Agallia quadripunctata (Provancher, 1872). “Polpis, June 25. July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930).

Agalliopsis novella (Say, 1830). “Sacacha Pond, July 19” (Johnson 1930, *Agallia novella* Say).

Amplicephalus littoralis (Ball, 1905). “The Creeks, June 22, 23” (Johnson 1930, *Deltocephalus littoralis* Ball).

Amphigonalia gothica (Signoret, 1854). “Polpis, Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930, *Cicadella gothica* Sign.).

Anoscopus albifrons (Linnaeus, 1758). “Maxcys Pond, June 21, Aug. 9. Polpis, July 27” (Johnson 1930, *Acucephalus albifrons* Linn.).

Aphrodes bicinctus (Schrank, 1776). “Common, Aug. 6–Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930, *Acucephalus nervosus* Schrank).

Balcanocerus provancheri (Van Duzee, 1890). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17–Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930, *Idiocerus provancheri* Van D.).

Balclutha impicta (Van Duzee, 1892). “Fair grounds, June 23” “Polpis, Aug. 6” (Johnson 1930, including *B. osborni* Van D.).

Cicadula smithi (Van Duzee, 1892). “Tom Nevers, June 22” (Johnson 1930, *Thamnotettix smithi* Van D.).

Chlorotettix unicolor (Fitch, 1851). “Fair grounds, Aug. 8. Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930).

Draeculacephala mollipes (Say, 1830). “Sacacha Pond, July 11–Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930).

Draeculacephala producta (Walker, F., 1851). “July 12 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930, *D. minor* Walk.).

Edwardsiana commissuralis (Stål, 1858). “Polpis, Sept. 11” (Johnson 1930, *Empoa commissuralis* Stål).

Edwardsiana flavescens (Fabricius, 1794). “Fair grounds, July 17” (Johnson 1930, *Empoasca flavescens* Fab.).

Edwardsiana rosae (Linnaeus, 1758). “Rose Leaf-hopper. Polpis, Aug. 6” (Johnson 1930, *Empoa rosae* Linn.).

Empoasca fabae (Harris, 1841). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930).

Endria inimicus (Say, 1830). “Maxcys Pond, July 16” (Johnson 1930, *Deltocephalus inimicus* Say).

Erythroneura comes (Say, 1825). “Grape Leaf-hopper. Maxcys Pond, Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930).

Extrusanus extrusus (Van Duzee, 1893). “July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930, *Euscelis extrusus* Van D.).

Flexamia sandersi (Osborn, 1907). “July 11 (Morse). Polpis, Aug. 6” (Johnson 1930, *Deltocephalus sandersi* Osb.).

Graminella nigrifrons (Forbes, S.A., 1885). “Maxcys and Sacacha Ponds, June 22 and July 19” (Johnson 1930, *Thamnotettix nigrifrons* Forbes).

Graphocephala coccinea (Forster, J.R., 1771). “Polpis, July 27–Aug. 16” (Johnson 1930, including var. *teliformis* Walk.).

* *Graphocephala hieroglyphica* (Say, 1830). On Virginia creeper, Tuckernuck, 9/10/2011 (BG 575191).

Gyponana striata (Burmeister, 1839). “Common, Aug. 19. Sept. 14, 1892 (Henshaw)” (Johnson 1930, *Gypona octolineata* var. *striata*).

Helochara communis Fitch, 1851. “Common, June 22–Sept. 8” (Johnson 1930).

Hymetta trifasciata (Say, 1825). “Polpis, Sept. 11” (Johnson 1930, *Erythroneura trifasciata* Say).

Idiodonus kennicotti (Uhler, 1864). “Small var. Fair grounds, July 17” (Johnson 1930, *Thamnotettix brittoni* Osb.).

* *Jikradia olitoria* (Say, 1830). On hazelnut, Stump Pond, 9/5/2019 (MMA).

Kybos obtusa (Walsh, 1862). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Empoasca obtusa* Walsh).

Macrosteles divisus (Uhler, 1877). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 7” (Johnson 1930, *Cicadula divisa* Uhl.).

Macrosteles sexnotatus (Fallén, 1806). “Common, June 23–Aug. 21” (Johnson 1930, *Cicadula sexnotata* Fall.).

Menosoma cinctum (Osborn & Ball, 1898). “Taupaushaw, Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930; *Eutettix cinctus* O. and B.).

Neohecalus lineatus (Uhler, 1877). “Common in salt marshes. Aug. 6–19” (Johnson 1930, *Hecalus lineatus* Uhl.).

Oncopsis nigrinasi (Fitch, 1851). “Polpis, Aug. 6, 1929” (Johnson 1930).

Ophiola decumanus (Kontkanen, 1949). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *O. striatula* Fall.).

Osbornellus auronitens (Provancher, 1889). “Hummock Pond, Sept. 9–13” (Johnson 1930, *Scaphoideus auronitens* Prov.).

* *Pagaronia minor* Anufriev, 1970. Siasconset, 6/16/2017 (BG 1400391).

Penthimia americana Fitch, 1851. Coskata Woods, 5/18/2012 (BG 734050); “Common, June 15–25. July (Morse)” (Johnson 1930).

Paraphlepsius fuscipennis (Van Duzee, 1892). “July 30” (Johnson 1930, *Phlepsius fuscipennis* Van D.)

Paraphlepsius irroratus (Say, 1830). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 7” (Johnson 1930, *Phlepsius irroratus* Say).

Polyamia obtecta (Osborn & Ball, 1898). “Grove Lane, June 21. July 16 (Brooks)” (Johnson 1930, *Deltocephalus obtectus* O. and B.).

Rossmoneura tecta (McAtee, 1920). “Polpis, Sept. 11” (Johnson 1930, *Erythroneura tecta* McAtee).

Scaphoideus immistus (Say, 1830). “Polpis, Aug. 6. Hummock Pond, Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930).

Scaphoideus sp. Nymph on *Viburnum dentatum*, State Forest, 6/10/2013 (BG 858233); on *Bidens connata*, Lily Pond Park, 9/9/2019 (BG 1734212); “Hummock Pond, Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930).

Scaphytopius acutus (Say, 1830). “Common, June 23–Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930, *Platymetopius acutus* Say).

Scaphytopius angustatus (Osborn, 1905). “Polpis, Aug. 6. Woods on the way to Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Platymetopius angustatus*).

Scaphytopius fulvus (Osborn, 1905). “Polpis, Aug. 6. Taupaushaw, Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930, *Platymetopius fulvus*).

Scaphytopius magdalensis (Provancher, 1889). “Polpis, Aug. 6” (Johnson 1930, *Platymetopius magdalensis*).

Scleroracus anthracinus (Van Duzee, 1894). “Sacacha and Maxcys Ponds, July 19 and 26” (Johnson 1930, *Euscelis anthracinus* Van D.).

Scleroracus arctostaphyli (Ball, 1899). “Common, July 4–Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Euscelis arctostaphyli* Ball).

Scleroracus osborni (Ball, 1928). “July 12 (Morse). Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Ophiola osborni* Ball).

Scleroracrus vaccinii (Van Duzee, 1890). “Common, July 4–Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930, *Euscelis vaccinii* Van D.).

Streptanus relativus (Gillette & Baker, 1895). “July 4 (Cushman)” “July 12 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930, *Euscelis deceptus* S. and DeL.; *E. relativus* G. and B.).

Typhlocyba sp. “Taupaushaw, July 25” (Johnson 1930).

Xestocephalus desertorum (Berg, 1879). “Tom Nevers, June 22. Polpis, July 27” (Johnson 1930, *X. brunneus* Van D.).

MEMBRACIDAE (Treehoppers)

Archasia auriculata (Fitch, 1851). “Taupaushaw and Polpis, July 25–Sept. 13. On oak” (Johnson 1930, *A. galeata* Fab.).

Ceresa bubalus (Fabricius, 1794). “Buffalo Tree-hopper. Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19. Taupaushaw, Sept. 7” (Johnson 1930).

Cyrtolobus puritanus Woodruff, 1924. “July 11 (Morse). Taupaushaw and Polpis, July 27–Aug. 17. On oak” (Johnson 1930).

Enchenopa latipes (Say, 1824). “Common, July 4–Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930, *Campylenchia latipes* Say (*curvata* Stål.).

* *Entyliia carinata* (Forster, J.R., 1771). Siasconset, 6/18/2017 (BG 1410369); on *Bidens connata*, Lily Pond Park, 9/9/2019 (BG 1734213).

Ophiderma flavicephala Goding, 1893. “Polpis, Aug. 6. On oak” (Johnson 1930).

* *Stictocephala bisonia* Kopp & Yonke, 1977. Photographed on *Bidens connata* at Lily Pond Park, 9/9/2019 (BG 1734216).

Stictocephala diceros (Say, 1824). “Polpis, Aug. 6. Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930, *Ceresa diceros* Say).

Stictocephala lutea (Walker, F., 1851). “Common, June 23–July 11. On oak” (Johnson 1930).

Telamona extrema Ball, 1903. “Maxcys Pond, Taupaushaw and Polpis, Aug. 7–Sept. 13. On oak (Johnson 1930).

FULGOROIDEA [=Fulgoridae in Johnson 1930] (Planthoppers)

CIXIIDAE

Melanoliarus franciscanus (Stål, 1859). “Taupaushaw, July 25, Aug. 5” (Johnson 1930, *Oliarus franciscanus* Stål).

Rossmoneura tecta (McAtee, 1920). “Sacacha Pond, July 19” (Johnson 1930, *Cixius basalis* Van D.).

DELPHACIDAE

Delphacodes puella (Van Duzee, 1897). “Shawkemo, June 24” (Johnson 1930).

Isodelphax basivitta (Van Duzee, 1909). “July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930, *Delphacodes basivitta* Van D.).

Muellerianella laminalis (Van Duzee, 1897). “Polpis, July 27 (Emerton)” (Johnson 1930, *Delphacodes lateralis* Van D.).

Muirodelphax arvensis (Fitch, 1851). “Common, June 24–Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930, *Delphacodes campestris* Van D.).

Muirodelphax sp. UMass Field Station, 5/19/2012 (BG 734056).

Nothodelphax lineatipes (Van Duzee, 1897). “Maxcys Pond, July 21” (Johnson 1930, *Delphacodes lineatipes* Van D.).

Pissonotus delicatus Van Duzee, 1897. “Tom Nevers, July 22, 1929” (Johnson 1930, *P. pallipes* Van D.).

Prokelisia crocea (Van Duzee, 1897). “Maxcys Pond, July 24. Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930, *Kelisia crocea* Van D.).

Prokelisia marginata (Van Duzee, 1897). “The Creeks, July 19, Aug. 21, 26” (Johnson 1930, including *P. setigera* Osb.).

Tumidagena terminalis (Metcalf, 1923). “The Creeks, Aug. 21, 26” (Johnson 1930, *Megamelanus terminalis* Metc.).

FLATIDAE

* *Flatormenis proxima* (Walker, F., 1851). Dead Horse Valley, 11/6/2017 (BG 1468048).

Sternorrhyncha (Plant-parasitic Hemipterans)

(Johnson 1930, p. 37)

APHIDOIDEA [=Aphiidae in Johnson 1930]

APHIDIDAE (Aphids)

* *Aphis spiraeicola* Patch, 1914. Collected on *Pluchea odorata* at Long Pond, 9/7/2019 (CNC).

Eriosoma americanum (Riley, 1879). Spring colonies on American elm roll the edges of the leaves downwards; in June migrate to shadbush roots, then return to elms to lay overwintering eggs on bark beginning in August. “On elms in the town” (Johnson 1930).

* *Hamamelistes spinosus* Shimer, 1867. Forms spiny bud galls on witch hazel and reddish swellings between the veins of birch leaves. Kelly Omand found a single gall at Coskata Woods in Sept. 2015.

* *Myzocallis* sp. On post oak; Saul’s Hills, 7/30/2017 (BG 1463109).

Pemphigus populicaulis Fitch, 1859. Forms galls on poplar leaves, at the junction of the blade and petiole. “On poplar, Taupaushaw” (Johnson 1930).

* *Staticobium* sp. On sea lavender. Masquetuck, 6/11/2013 (BG 1169945; BG 1169946; ASJ; Eiseman & Jensen 2015) and 6/30/2014, collected by Kelly Omand (CNC).

* *Tamalia coweni* (Cockerell, 1905). Forms reddish galls on bearberry leaves. 9/8/2011; State Forest (8/8/2012).

* *Tetraneura* sp. Elm leaf galls; in town (9/10/2011).

COCCOIDEA [=Coccidae in Johnson 1930]

COCCIDAE (Soft Scale Insects)

Mesolecanium nigrofasciatum (Pergande, 1898). Terrapin Scale. “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Lecanium nigrofasciatum* Perg.).

DIASPIDIDAE (Armored Scale Insects)

Aulacaspis rosae (Virey, 1821). Rose Scale. “On rambler rose at Library, Sept. 9” (Johnson 1930, *Aulacaspis rosae* Bouché).

Lepidosaphes ulmi (Linnaeus, 1758). Oyster-shell Scale. “On various trees and shrubs” (Johnson 1930).

PHYLLOXEROIDEA [=Phylloxeridae in Johnson 1930]

ADELGIDAE

Adelges abietis (Linnaeus, 1758). Forms pineapple-like galls on spruce twigs. “On spruce in the yard of Mr. Sidney Chase” (Johnson 1930).

PHYLLOXERIDAE

* *Phylloxera* sp. Leaf gall on mockernut hickory; Squam Swamp (6/9/2016).

* *Phylloxerina nyssae* (Pergande, 1904). Forms crescent-shaped galls along the margins of tupelo leaves. Almanac Pond (8/4/2012); Coskata Woods (8/6/2012); Squam Swamp (8/8/2012).

PSYLLOIDEA [=Chermidae in Johnson 1930]

LIVIIDAE

Livia bifasciata Provancher, 1886. Forms galls in *Juncus canadensis* inflorescences. Pout Ponds (7/25/2014, 7/30/2017; BG 1462525; CSE); Sanford Farm (8/27/2015). “June 25–July 19” (Johnson 1930, *Livia maculipennis* (Fitch)).

PSYLLIDAE

Arytaina genistae (Latreille, 1804). Broom Psyllid. Introduced from Europe; on Scotch broom and other legumes. “Woods on road to Taupaushaw, June 26, 1928” (Johnson 1930).

* *Cacopsylla annulata* (Fitch, 1851). On maple. Squam Swamp, 6/9/2016 (BG 1302403; CM).

Cacopsylla quadrilineata (Fitch, 1851). On willow. “June 25–Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930, *Psylla quadrilineata* Fitch).

* *Cacopsylla rara* (Tuthill, 1944). Recorded from *Viburnum* in western Canada. Adult found on a sweet pepperbush leaf near exuviae, but may have blown from nearby arrowwood. Squam Swamp, 6/9/2016 (BG 1302462; CM).

TRIOZIDAE

Phylloplecta tripunctata (Fitch, 1851). Blackberry Psyllid. The nymph lives on the underside of the terminal leaves of blackberry, causing them to curl and form rosette-like bunches (Johnson 1930, *Trioza tripunctata* Fitch).

COLEOPTERA (Beetles)

BUPRESTOIDEA

BUPRESTIDAE (Jewel Beetles, Metallic Wood-boring Beetles)
(Johnson 1930, p. 52)

* *Agrilus cuprescens* (Ménétries, 1832). Rose Stem Girdler, Bronze Cane Borer. Introduced from Europe; larvae bore in stems of rose, raspberry, and currant/gooseberry. On wild rose, Head of the Plains, 6/10/2016 (BG 1302562).

Agrilus defectus LeConte, 1860. Larvae bore in oaks of the white oak group. “Polpis, June 25” (Johnson 1930).

Agrilus imbellis Crotch, 1873. “July (*Miss Harwood*). Fair grounds, Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930).

Agrilus otiosus Say, 1833. Larvae bore in various hardwoods. “Polpis, June 25. Wood on road to Taupaushaw, July 25” (Johnson 1930).

Agrilus ruficollis (Fabricius, 1787). Red-necked Cane Borer. Larvae bore in stems of blackberry and raspberry, causing gall-like swellings. “Common, June 24–Aug. 16” (Johnson 1930).

Agrilus sayi Saunders, 1870. Larvae bore in bayberry and sweetfern. “Common, June 23–July 27” (Johnson 1930, *A. lateralis* Say).

Brachys aerosus (Melsheimer, 1845). Larvae mine in oak leaves. “Common, June 25–Aug. 16” (Johnson 1930). Feeding on scrub oak, Squam Farm, 6/9/2013 (BG 858219); feeding on scrub oak, Pout Ponds, 6/9/2016.

Brachys aeruginosus Gory, 1841. Larvae mine in oak leaves. “Polpis, July 27. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*). On bayberry” (Johnson 1930). Coskata Woods, 5/18/2012 (BG 734048); nibbling on a *Crocantemum* leaf, Head of the Plains, 6/10/2016 (BG 1302539; ZFMK).

* *Brachys howdeni* Hesperheide, 2016. Larvae mine in trailing arbutus leaves. Larva collected at Milestone Road, 5/20/2012, adult emerged 5/31/2012 (paratype, USNM; Hesperheide & Eiseman 2016); young larvae near Madequecham, 8/3/2012.

* *Brachys ovatus* (Weber, 1801). Larvae mine in oak leaves. Gardner Farm, 6/13/2013 (BG 859550); leaf mines on scrub oak, Pout Ponds, 8/29/2015, adults emerged June 2016 (ZFMK).

CHRYSOMELOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, pp. 59–65)

CERAMBYCIDAE (Long-horned Beetles)

Cerambycinae

Megacyllene robiniae (Forster, 1771). Locust Borer. “‘Nantucket’ (*Miss Hussey*)” (Johnson 1930, *Cyllene robiniae* Forst.).

Neoclytus acuminatus (Fabricius, 1775). Red-headed Ash Borer. “Fair grounds, June 23. Larva in a variety of hard woods” (Johnson 1930).

Tilloclytus geminatus (Haldeman, 1847). “Polpis, June 25. Larva in oak, dogwood, sour gum, etc.” (Johnson 1930).

Lamiinae (Flat-faced Longhorns)

Eupogonius tomentosus (Haldeman, 1847). “Fair grounds, June 24. Larva in pine” (Johnson 1930).

Hyperplatys aspersa (Say, 1824). “Maxcys Pond, June 24. Polpis, Aug. 6. Larva recorded from willow, dogwood, wild cherry, etc.” (Johnson 1930).

Oberea myops Haldeman, 1847. Rhododendron Stem Borer. “Maxcys Pond, Taupaushaw and Sacacha Ponds, June 24–Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930).

Oberea perspicillata Haldeman, 1847. Raspberry Cane Borer; Blackberry Cane Girdler. “June 25–July 24. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *O. bimaculata* Oliv.). Girdled blackberry stems observed at Coffin Park, 8/7/2012.

Pogonocherus mixtus Haldeman, 1847. “Muskeget, July 14, 1924 (*Brooks*). Larva in pine and willow” (Johnson 1930).

Psenocerus supernotatus (Say, 1823). Currant-tip Borer. “Hummock Pond, June 25. Larva in elm, poplar, willow, currant, etc.” (Johnson 1930).

* *Tetraopes tetrophthalmus* (Forster, 1771). Red Milkweed Beetle. Characteristic adult feeding damage observed on common milkweed outside Maria Mitchell museum, 8/2/2012.

Lepturinae (Flower Longhorns)

Analeptura lineola (Say, 1824). Larvae bore in Betulaceae and pine. “Polpis, June 25” (Johnson 1930, *Strangalepta lineola* Say).

Desmocerus palliatus (Forster, 1771). Elderberry Borer. “Grove Lane, Aug. 9” (Johnson 1930).

Strangalia luteicornis (Fabricius, 1775). “Grove Lane, June 21 and July 20. Maxcys Pond, July 16. July 3 (*Cushman*). Larva in elm, beech, grape, and viburnum” (Johnson 1930, *Ophistomis luteicornis* Fab.). Photographed by “Mthew”, 7/12/2011 (BG 547686).

Trachysida mutabilis (Newman, 1841). “Polpis, June 25. Larva in oak, maple, birch, etc.” (Johnson 1930, *Leptura mutabilis*).

Prioninae

* *Prionus laticollis* (Drury, 1773). Broad-necked Root Borer. Adult photographed by Craig Biegler, 7/19/2007 (BG 128748).

CHRYSOMELIDAE (Leaf Beetles)

Bruchinae (Pea and Bean Weevils)

Larvae in this subfamily feed and pupate inside seeds.

Acanthoscelides calvus (Horn, 1873). “July 16–Aug. 8. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Mylabris calvus* Horn). This record requires confirmation, since Johnson (1930) states that both this and “*Mylabris ater*” are common in the seedpods of Scotch Broom. This species has sometimes been misidentified as *Bruchidius villosus*, and its only known host is *Crocantemum canadense* (Kingsolver 2004). Adults of an unidentified *Acanthoscelides* species were photographed on *Crocantemum* flowers at Pout Ponds, 6/9/2016 (BG 1302492).

Acanthoscelides obtectus (Say, 1831). Bean Weevil. “Infests dried beans” (Johnson 1930, *Mylabris obtectus* Say).

* *Althaeus* sp. Emerging from seeds of *Hibiscus moscheutos*, Quaise, October 2019 (MLBM; BG 1770813).

Bruchidius villosus (Fabricius, 1792). Broom Seed Beetle. Introduced from Europe; in seedpods of Scotch Broom. “June 23–Aug. 24” (Johnson 1930, *Mylabris ater* Marsh.).

Cassidinae (Tortoise Beetles and Hispines)

Larvae of tortoise beetles feed externally on leaves, holding a “shield” of shed skins and excrement over their backs. The four species found on Nantucket all feed on bindweeds and morning glories (Convolvulaceae). The two hispines are leafminers on Asteraceae.

Charidotella purpurata (Boheman, 1855). “Sacacha Pond, Aug. 16” (Johnson 1930, *Metriona purpurata*).

Charidotella sexpunctata bicolor (Fabricius, 1798). Golden Tortoise Beetle. “Sacacha Pond, June 24” (Johnson 1930, *Metriona bicolor* Fab.).

Chelymorpha cassidea (Fabricius, 1775). Argus Tortoise Beetle. “June 24–Aug. 19. Tuckernuck, June 22 (*Brooks*). Common on *Convolvulus*” (Johnson 1930).

Deloyala guttata (Olivier, 1790). Mottled Tortoise Beetle. “July 3 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Chirida guttata* Oliv.); adult at Gardner Farm, 6/13/2013 (BG 859555); adults on *Calystegia* at Lily Pond Park, 9/24/2020 (BG 1940117, BG 1940121).

Microrhopala vittata (Fabricius, 1798). Goldenrod Leafminer. “The Creeks, Aug. 21–Sept. 11” (Johnson 1930); larvae mining *Solidago rugosa* at Sanford Farm, 7/27/2017 (ZFMK).

Sumitrosis inaequalis (Weber, 1801). Larvae mine leaves of Asteraceae. “Maxcys Pond, June 22–25. Grove Lane, July 20” (Johnson 1930, *Anoplitis inaequalis* Web.); larvae mining *Symphyotrichum undulatum* at Stump Pond, 7/30/2017 (ZFMK).

Chrysomelinae

Larvae in this subfamily feed externally on leaves, without a fecal covering.

Calligrapha californica Linell, 1896. On *Bidens*. “June 7–Aug. 20. Tuckernuck, July 21” (Johnson 1930, *C. elegans* Oliv.).

Calligrapha lunata (Fabricius, 1787). Moon-marked Leaf Beetle. On rose. “Common, June 21–Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930).

* *Calligrapha rhoda* Knab, 1909. On hazelnut. Adult photographed on Tuckernuck, 9/10/2011 (BG 575158).

Leptinotarsa decemlineata (Say, 1824). Colorado Potato Beetle. “June 8–Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930).

Prasocuris obliquata J. L. LeConte, 1866. “Grove Lane, June 21. Maxcys Pond, July 21” (Johnson 1930).

Zygogramma suturalis (Fabricius, 1775). Ragweed Leaf Beetle. “Grove Lane, Aug. 16. The Creeks, Sept. 21” (Johnson 1930).

Criocerinae

Crioceris asparagi (Linnaeus, 1758). Common Asparagus Beetle. “June 21–July 20” (Johnson 1930).

Crioceris duodecimpunctata (Linnaeus, 1758). Twelve-spotted Asparagus Beetle. “June 21” (Johnson 1930).

* *Oulema palustris* (Blatchley, 1913). Larvae mining leaves of *Cirsium horridulum*, Head of the Plains, 6/10/2016, adults emerged July 1–13 (BG 1309886; MLBM); larvae at Cisco Beach, 6/11/2016.

Cryptocephalinae (Case-bearing Leaf Beetles)

Larvae in this subfamily live in portable cases made of their own excrement, sometimes incorporating plant debris. Many live in leaf litter; some are found on leaves of their host plants. Unidentified adults were photographed at Polpis bike path, 7/25/2014 (BG 1016546, subtribe Cryptocephalina), on oak at Pout Ponds, 6/9/2016 (BG 1302529, *Pachybrachis* sp.), and on bayberry at Smooth Hummocks, 6/14/2018 (BG 1633620, *Pachybrachis* sp.).

Anomoea laticlavia (Forster, 1771). Clay-colored Leaf Beetle. “Wood east of Hummock Pond, June 21. July 5 (*Cushman*). Fair Grounds, July. On locust (*Robinia*)” (Johnson 1930, *Antipus laticlavia*).

Bassareus formosus (F. E. Melsheimer, 1847). “East side of Hummock, June 21 (*Emerton*). Polpis, Aug. 6. On ‘Elder’” (Johnson 1930).

Bassareus lituratus (Fabricius, 1801). “Fair grounds, June 23 and July 17” (Johnson 1930).

Bassareus mammifer (Newman, 1840). “Sacacha Pond, June 24, 1926. Maxcys Pond, June 24, 1928. On hazel” (Johnson 1930, *B. mammifer* var. *luteipennis* Melsh.).

Cryptocephalus gibbicollis Haldeman, 1849. “Taupaushaw, June 19 (*Emerton*). Sacacha Pond, July 19. On huckleberry” (Johnson 1930).

Cryptocephalus guttulatus Olivier, 1808. Fourteen-spotted Leaf Beetle. “Tom Nevers, June 22 (*Emerton*)–July 4 (*Cushman*). Sacacha Pond, July 19. On oak” (Johnson 1930).

Cryptocephalus incertus Olivier, 1808. “Maxcys Pond and Taupaushaw, Sept. 13 and 14. On cranberry” (Johnson 1930).

Cryptocephalus insertus Haldeman, 1849. “Maxcys Pond, June 24. July 30 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Cryptocephalus notatus Fabricius, 1787. “Common, June 23–July 16. On oak, blackberry, etc.” (Johnson 1930).

Cryptocephalus quadruplex Newman, 1841. “Sacacha Pond, June 24 and July 19” (Johnson 1930).

Diachus auratus (Fabricius, 1801). Bronze Leaf Beetle. “Maxcys Pond, July 16” (Johnson 1930).

Lexiphanes saponatus (Fabricius, 1801). Larvae on leatherleaf. “Maxcys Pond, July 21 and Sept. 8” (Johnson 1930, *Monachus saponatus* Fab.).

Neochlamisus cribripennis (J. L. LeConte, 1878). “Fair grounds, June 23–July 19. Maxcys Pond, Sept. 8–13” (Johnson 1930).

Neochlamisus gibbosus (Fabricius, 1777). “Aug. 17 (*Emerton*). Surfside, Sept. 12. The larva lives in a case, on blackberry” (Johnson 1930, *Chlamys gibbosa* Fab.).

Pachybrachis femoratus (Olivier, 1808). “June–July 26. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Pachybrachys femoratus* var. *aquilonis* Fall).

Pachybrachis hepaticus (F. E. Melsheimer, 1847). “Maxcys Pond and Grove Lane, July 14–20” (Johnson 1930).

Pachybrachis luridus (Fabricius, 1798). “Common, June 23–July 16” (Johnson 1930).

Pachybrachis obsoletus Suffrian, 1852. “Maxcys Pond and Surfside, July 20–26” (Johnson 1930).

Pachybrachis othonus (Say, 1825). “July 3 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Pachybrachis peccans Suffrian, 1852. “Common, June 7–July 26” (Johnson 1930).

Pachybrachis relictus Fall, 1915. “Fair grounds, June 23–July 19” (Johnson 1930).

Saxinis omogera Lacordaire, 1848. “July 4 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Triachus atomus (Suffrian, 1852). “Common, June 23–July 25. On bayberry” (Johnson 1930).

Triachus cerinus J. L. LeConte, 1880. “Maxcys Pond, June 25 and July 16. Fair grounds, July 19” (Johnson 1930).

Donaciinae (Aquatic Leaf Beetles)

Larvae in this subfamily feed on the submerged stems of aquatic plants.

Donacia subtilis Kunze, 1818. “Polpis, July 21 (*Brooks*)” (Johnson 1930).

Neohaemonia nigricornis (Kirby, 1837). “Hummock Pond, Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930, *Haemonia nigricornis* Kirby).

Plateumaris flavipes (Kirby, 1837). “Maxcys Pond, June 7–25” (Johnson 1930, *Donacia flavipes* Kirby).

Plateumaris metallica (Ahrens, 1810). “Maxcys Pond, June 7–22” (Johnson 1930, *Donacia metallica* Ahr.).

Plateumaris robusta (Schaeffer, 1920). “Maxcys Pond, June 7–25” (Johnson 1930, *Donacia pusilla* var. *robusta* Schffr.).

Eumolpinae (Oval Leaf Beetles)

Larvae in this subfamily are subterranean root feeders.

Chrysochus auratus (Fabricius, 1775). Dogbane Beetle. “Near Surfside (*Royal E. Robbins*)” (Johnson 1930).

Colaspis brunnea (Fabricius, 1798). “Maxcys Pond, July 24. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Colaspis costipennis Crotch, 1873. “Maxcys Pond, July 20. On grape” (Johnson 1930, *C. brunnea* var. *costipennis* Cr.).

Graphops curtipennis (F. E. Melsheimer, 1847). “Sept. 14 (*Henshaw*)” (Johnson 1930).

Metachroma quercatum (Fabricius, 1801). “Sacacha Pond, June 24. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*). On oak” (Johnson 1930).

* *Paria aterrima* (Olivier, 1808). Mating on marsh elder, Masquetuck, 6/14/2018 (BG 1633822; MMA).

Spintherophyta globosa (Olivier, 1808). “Common, July 3–Sept. 21” (Johnson 1930, *Chrysodina globosa* Oliv.); mating on ?hazelnut leaf, Squam Swamp, 6/12/2014 (BG 859528).

Xanthonia decemnotata (Say, 1824). Ten-spotted Leaf Beetle. “Coskata, May 17 (*Emerton*). Sacacha Pond, June 24 and Sept. 10. On oak” (Johnson 1930).

Galerucinae (Skeletonizing Leaf Beetles and Flea Beetles)

Acalymma vittatum (Fabricius, 1775). Striped Cucumber Beetle. “June 9–23” (Johnson 1930, *Diabrotica vittata* Fab.).

Altica amoena Horn, 1889. “Surfside, Sept. 9” (Johnson 1930, *Haltica amaena* Horn).

Altica kalmiae (F. E. Melsheimer, 1847). On laurel (*Kalmia*). “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17 and Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930, *Haltica kalmiae* Melsh.); larvae on swamp azalea at Squam Swamp, 6/16/2018, adults emerged by 8/5/2018 (MLBM).

Altica knabii Blatchley, 1910. On evening primrose. “Maxcys Pond, Aug. 8 and Sept. 8. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Haltica knabi* Blanch.).

Altica litigata Fall, 1910. On Onagraceae. “Grove Lane, June 22 (*Emerton*)” (Johnson 1930, *Haltica litigata* Fall).

Altica rosae Woods, 1918. On wild rose. “Taupaushaw, May 18 (*Emerton*). Sacacha Pond, June 24, Sept. 11” (Johnson 1930, *Haltica rosae* Woods).

Blepharida rhois (Forster, 1771). Sumac Flea Beetle. “May 8 (*Emerton*). Taupaushaw, Aug. 17–Sept. 14. On sumac. The larva is covered by excrement” (Johnson 1930).

Capraita subvittata (Horn, 1889). “Common, May 18–Sept. 12” (Johnson 1930, *Oedionychis subvittata* Horn).

Chaetocnema confinis Crotch, 1873. Sweetpotato Flea Beetle. Larvae feed in roots of Convolvulaceae. “Maxcys Pond, June 25–July 24” (Johnson 1930).

Chaetocnema minuta F. E. Melsheimer, 1847. “Grove Lane, June 22 (*Emerton*)” (Johnson 1930).

Diabrotica undecimpunctata Mannerheim, 1843. Spotted Cucumber Beetle. “July 4–Sept. 11” (Johnson 1930, *D. duodecimpunctata*). Lily Pond Park, 7/28/2017.

Disonycha collata (Fabricius, 1801). On Caryophyllales. “Coskata Pond, May 17, 1929 (*Emerton*)” (Johnson 1930).

Disonycha pennsylvanica (Illiger, 1807). On smartweed (*Persicaria*). “Common on *Polygonum*, May 17–Sept. 9” (Johnson 1930, *Disconycha pennsylvanica* Ill.). Adult photographed at Little Sesachacha Pond, 8/4/2012 (BG 741261).

Disonycha xanthomelas (Dalman, 1823). Spinach Flea Beetle. “Common on sea sand wort (*Arenaria peploides*). July 14, Aug. 24 (*Sanford*). Sept. 12” (Johnson 1930, *Disconycha xanthomelaena* Dalm.).

Epitrix cucumeris (Harris, 1851). Potato Flea Beetle. “Common, June 23–Aug. 17. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Erynephala maritima (J. L. LeConte, 1865). Reared from larvae mining in *Salicornia* stems, Masquetuck, 7/28/2017 (MLBM). “Muskeget, June 14, 1924.” (Johnson 1930, *Monoxia puncticollis* Say (*maritima* Lec.)).

Kuschelina gibbitarsa (Say, 1824). On Lamiaceae. “Shawkemo, June 23. Sacacha Pond, Sept. 10” (Johnson 1930, *Oedionychis gibbitarsa* Say).

Kuschelina miniata (Fabricius, 1801). “Sacacha Pond, June 27” (Johnson 1930, *Oedionychis miniata* Fab.).

Kuschelina vians (Illiger, 1807). On smartweed (*Persicaria*). “Maxcys Pond, June 22” (Johnson 1930, *Oedionychis vivans* Ill.).

Longitarsus erro Horn, 1889. “Grove Lane, June 22 (*Emerton*)” (Johnson 1930).

Mantura floridana Crotch, 1873. Larvae are leafminers on *Rumex* and other Polygonaceae. “Hummock Pond and Grove Lane, June 7 and July 20” (Johnson 1930).

Ophraella americana (Fabricius, 1801). On goldenrod. “Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Galerucella americana* Fab.).

* *Ophraella notata* (Fabricius, 1801). Feeding on boneset (*Eupatorium perfoliatum*) foliage at Lily Pond Park, 7/28/2017 (BG 1461829).

Phyllotreta chalybeipennis (Crotch, 1873). Larvae mine leaves of sea rocket. “July 14” (Johnson 1930); adults and larvae at Eel Point, 7/26/2014, adults emerged August 14–21 (BG 1036929; BG 1036931; MLBM; Eiseman 2015a).

* *Phyllotreta cruciferae* (Goeze, 1777). Crucifer Flea Beetle. Introduced from Eurasia. Adult collected on sea rocket, Eel Point, 7/26/2014 (BG 1036926; MLBM).

Phyllotreta striolata (Fabricius, 1801). Introduced from Palearctic; larvae feed on roots of Brassicaceae. “Sacacha Pond, June 21. Polpis, July 28. Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *P. sinuata* Steph.). Undated specimen in INHS (Smith 1985).

Psylliodes punctulatus F. E. Melsheimer, 1847. “Metacomet Pond, June 24. On dock” (Johnson 1930, *P. punctulata* Melsh.).

* *Pyrrhalta viburni* (Paykull, 1799). Viburnum Leaf Beetle. Introduced from Europe; causing widespread defoliation of viburnums in the northeastern US. Larvae on arrowwood, Elin Anderwald’s driveway, 6/9/2016, adult emerged July 14 (MMA); larvae abundant at Thad Jones’ house, 6/19/2017; feeding damage observed at Masquetuck, 6/14/2018.

Strabala rufa (Illiger, 1807). On buttonweed (*Diodia*). “Maxcys Pond, June 7–22. Shawkemo, June 23” (Johnson 1930, *Haltica rufa* Ill.).

Systema hudsonias (Forster, 1771). “Smartweed Flea Beetle. June 21–July 27” (Johnson 1930).

Tricholochmaea cavicollis (J. L. LeConte, 1865). Cherry Leaf Beetle. “Coleman Bird Sanctuary, June 8. Taupaushaw, Sept. 14. On plum and cherry” (Johnson 1930, *Galerucella cavicollis* Lec.).

Tricholochmaea kalmiae (Fall, 1924). On laurel (*Kalmia*). “Maxcys Pond, June 22. Taupaushaw, Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930, *Galerucella kalmiae* Fall).

* *Trirhabda bacharidis* (Weber, 1801). Groundselbush Beetle. Larvae on *Baccharis halimifolia*, Masquetuck, 6/11/2013 (BG 858905); larvae at Sheep Pond, 6/15/2018, adults emerged by 7/15/2018 (MLBM).

Trirhabda canadensis (Kirby, 1837). Goldenrod Leaf Beetle. “Aug. 2–Sept. 8. Common on the golden rod along the shore” (Johnson 1930).

Trirhabda virgata J. L. LeConte, 1865. On goldenrod. “Polpis, Aug. 6. Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930).

MEGALOPODIDAE (Megalopodid Leaf Beetles)

* *Zeugophora* sp. Reyes Pond, 9/6/2019 (BG 1729891).

CURCULIONOIDEA (Snout and Bark Beetles) (Johnson 1930, pp. 65–69)

ANTHRIBIDAE (Fungus Weevils)

Trigonorhinus rotundatus (LeConte, 1876). “Taupaushaw, July 25 (*Emerton*). Polpis, July 27, Sept. 14 (*Frost*)” (Johnson 1930, *Anthribulus rotundatus* Lec.).

Trigonorhinus sticticus (Boheman, 1833). “Sacacha Pond, June 24. Polpis, June 25–Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930, *Brachytarsus sticticus* Boh.).

ATTELABIDAE

Attelabinae (Leaf-rolling Weevils)

Adults roll portions of leaves into cylindrical rolls in which the larvae develop.

Himatolabus pubescens (Say 1826). On oak, alder, and hazelnut. “Sacacha Pond, June 24 and Aug. 16. On sumac and hazel” (Johnson 1930, *Attelabus rhois* Boh.).

Homoeolabus analis (Illiger, 1794). On oak. “Taupaushaw and Polpis, July 25–27. On sumac” (Johnson 1930, *Attelabus analis* Ill.).

Synolabus nigripes (LeConte, 1824). On sumac. “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17 and Sept. 14. On oak” (Johnson 1930, *Attelabus nigripes* Lec.). Mating and rolling leaves on winged sumac, UMass field station, 6/11/2013 (BG 859103).

Pterocolinae (Thief Weevils)

Pterocolus ovatus (Fabricius, 1801). Adults eat eggs of leaf-rolling weevils and then lay their own eggs in the rolls. “Taupaushaw and Polpis, July 25 and July 27. On oak (Johnson 1930).

Rhynchitinae (Leaf and Bud Weevils)

Eugnamptus angustatus (Herbst, 1797). Larvae mine dead leaves of sassafras and other trees and shrubs in the leaf litter. “Fair grounds, June 23–July 19. On oak” (Johnson 1930, *E. collaris* Fab.; *E. collaris* var. *fuscipes* Pierce).

Hamiltoniauletes cassandrae (LeConte, 1876). “Polpis, June 25 (*Emerton*). Sept. 17–21 (*Henshaw*)” (Johnson 1930, *Auletes albovestita* Blatch.).

Temnocerus aeratus (Say, 1831). “Maxcys Pond, June 7–25. Polpis, July 27. On oak. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Rhynchites aeratus* Say).

Temnocerus perplexus (Blatchley, 1916). “Fair grounds, June 23. Surfside, July 25. Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Rhynchites perplexus* Blatch.).

BRACHYCERIDAE

Eirrhiniinae (Marsh Weevils)

Brachybamus electus Germar, 1835. On various aquatic plants. “June 24” (Johnson 1930).

Notaris puncticollis (LeConte, 1876). On arrow arum. “June 23, 1922” (Johnson 1930).

Notiodes limatulus (Gyllenhal, 1836). On bulrushes. “Surfside, July 20. Sacacha Pond, July 19. July 30 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Endalus limatulus* Gyll.).

Notiodes ovalis (LeConte, 1876). “Common, June 24–Aug. 20. Muskeget, July 14” (Johnson 1930, *Endalus ovalis* Lec.).

Onychylis nigrirostris (Boheman, 1843). Pickerelweed Weevil. “Sacacha Pond, June 24. On *Sagittaria*” (Johnson 1930).

BRENTIDAE (Primitive Weevils)

Apioninae (Pear-shaped Weevils)

* *Coelocephalapion* sp. Collected from *Mikania scandens* at Windswept Cranberry Bogs, 9/24/2020 (CSE, BG 1940445).

Fallapion pensylvanicum (Boheman, 1839). On wild parsnip and water hemlock. “Maxcys Pond, June 25 and July 16” (Johnson 1930, *Apion pensylvanicum* Boh.).

Neapion herculanum (Smith, 1884). On arrowwood. “Sacacha Pond, July 19. Polpis, Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930, *Apion puritanum* Fall.). Hiding in *Marmara* bark flap on arrowwood, State Forest, 6/11/2016 (BG 1302582).

Perapion punctinasum (J.B. Smith, 1884). On docks (*Rumex* spp.). “Maxcys Pond, June 7. Sacacha Pond, June 24” (Johnson 1930, *Apion punctinasum* Sm.).

Trichapion rostrum (Say, 1826). Larvae develop in seedpods of wild indigo. “Common, July 23–30. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Apion rostrum* Say). Adult on *Baptisia tinctoria*, Pout Ponds, 6/9/2016 (BG 1302524).

CURCULIONIDAE (Snout and Bark Beetles)

Bagoinae

Bagous americanus LeConte, 1876. Larvae mine leaves of waterlilies. “Sacacha and Maxcys Ponds, June 24 and July 16” (Johnson 1930).

Baridinae (Flower Weevils)

Baris interstitialis (Say, 1824). “Sacacha Pond, July 24” (Johnson 1930, *B. subaenea* Lec.).

Cosmobaris scolopacea (Germar, 1824). Beet Petiole Borer. “Madeket, July 16. Grove Lane, Aug. 9. On ragweed (Johnson 1930, *Baris scolopacea* Germ.).

Madarellus undulatus (Say, 1824). On grape and Virginia creeper. “Polpis, Sept. 13 (*Frost*)” (Johnson 1930).

Nicentrus lecontei Champion, 1908. “Woods on road to Taupaushaw, July 25” (Johnson 1930).

Nicentrus puritanus Casey, 1920. “Common, July 16–Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930).

Odontocorynus scutellumalbum (Say, 1831). “July 3 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Pseudobaris nigrina (Say, 1831). “The Creeks, Aug. 21” (Johnson 1930).

Ceutorhynchinae (Minute Seed Weevils)

Acanthoscelidius acephalus (Say, 1824). “June 22–July 24. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*). On evening primrose” (Johnson 1930, *Acanthoscelis acephalus* Say).

Ceutorhynchus pusio Mannerheim, 1852. “‘Nantucket.’ On sea rocket” (Johnson 1930).

Ceutorhynchus quadridens (Panzer, 1795). “June 21–July 27. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*). On cabbage” (Johnson 1930).

Parauleutes nebulosus (LeConte, 1876). “Sacacha Pond, June 24–July 14. Fair grounds, Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930, *Auleutes nebulosus* Lec.).

Pelenomus sulcicollis (Fåhraeus, 1843). “Miacomet Pond, June 24. On *Polygonum*” (Johnson 1930). Larva feeding on starflower leaf, Squam Swamp, 6/9/2016.

Rhinoncus pyrrhopus Boheman, 1845. “Shawkemo, June 23. On *Rumex*” (Johnson 1930).

Cryptorhynchinae (Hidden Snout Weevils)

Tyloderma aereum (Say, 1831). “Shawkemo, June 23, 1927” (Johnson 1930, *T. aerea* Say).

Curculioninae

Anthonomus disjunctus LeConte, 1876. “July 16–Sept. 13. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Anthonomus musculus Say, 1831. “June 25–July 27. On huckleberry” (Johnson 1930).

Anthonomus nubilus LeConte, 1876. “Maxcys Pond, July 24” (Johnson 1930).

Anthonomus profundus LeConte, 1876. “July 16–Aug. 16. On *Crataegus*” (Johnson 1930).

Anthonomus pusillus LeConte, 1876. “June 24–Aug. 8. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Anthonomus signatus Say, 1831. Strawberry Bud Weevil. “June 25–July 27. It also frequents blackberry and raspberry” (Johnson 1930).

Anthonomus univestis Schenkling and Marshall, 1934. “July 16 (*Brooks*). Maxcys Pond, July 24” (Johnson 1930, *A. uniformis* Blatch.).

Anthonomus sp. “Coleman Bird Sanctuary, June 8. Maxcys Pond, June 26” (Johnson 1930).

* *Curculio* sp. Acorn Weevil. Adult on underside of scrub oak leaf, Squam Farm, 6/9/2013 (BG 783580).

* *Isochnus sequensi* (Stierlin, 1894). Leafminer on Salicaceae; introduced from Europe. Leaf mines on quaking aspen, Polpis Bike Path by Don Allen’s, 8/29/2015; leaf mines on basket willow, UMass field station, 8/29/2015, adults emerged 9/8/2015 (MMA).

Myrmex myrmex (Herbst, 1797). “Surfside, July 20. It is inquiline in cynipid galls” (Johnson 1930, *Otidocephalus myrmex* Hbst.).

* *Orchestes mixtus* Blatchley, 1916. Leafminer on hazelnut. Mines on *Corylus americana*, Squam Farm, 6/9/2013; mines on *C. cornuta*, Squam Swamp and Coskata Woods, 6/12/2013.

Orchestes pallicornis Say, 1831. Larvae mine leaves of rosaceous trees and shrubs. “Polpis, July 27. On willow” (Johnson 1930). Mines on *Prunus maritima* and *P. serotina*, Dead Horse Valley, 6/9/2012; mines on *P. serotina*, Squam Swamp, 6/12/2013; adult and mines on *P. serotina*, Gardner Farm, 6/13/2013; mines on *P. maritima*, Eel Point, 7/26/2014

Piazorhinus scutellaris (Say, 1826). On oak. “Taupaushaw, July 25” (Johnson 1930).

Pseudanthonomus crataegi (Walsh, 1867). “Taupaushaw, May 18. July 25 and Aug. 16 (*Emerton*)” (Johnson 1930).

Rhinusa tetra (Fabricius, 1792). Larvae develop in mullein seedpods. “Fair grounds, June 23. Common on mullein” (Johnson 1930, *Gymnetron tetrum* Fab.).

Cyclominae (Underwater Weevils)

Listronotus sparsus (Say, 1831). “The Creeks, Aug. 21” (Johnson 1930, *L. latiusculus* Boh.).

Dryophthorinae

Sitophilus granarius (Linnaeus, 1758). Granary Weevil. “Infests stored grain” (Johnson 1930, *Calendra granaria* Linn.).

Sphenophorus cariosus (Olivier, 1807). Nutgrass Billbug. On sedges. “Maxcys Pond, June 7–22 (*Emerton*). Surfside, Aug. 20” (Johnson 1930).

Sphenophorus costipennis Horn, 1873. “Sacacha Pond, June 24” (Johnson 1930).

Sphenophorus necydaloides (Fabricius, 1801). “‘Nantucket’ (*Dimmock*). Surfside, Aug. 2–16 (*Sanford*)” (Johnson 1930, *S. retusus* Gyll.); “Aug. 18 and 27 (*Sanford*). Surfside, Sept. 12 (*Frost*)” (Johnson 1930).

* *Sphenophorus parvulus* Gyllenhal, 1838. Bluegrass Billbug. On beach at Eel Point, 7/26/2014 (BG 1018138).

* *Sphenophorus pertinax pertinax* (Olivier, 1807). Host is *Spartina*. On beach along Madaket harbor, 5/28/2012, photographed by Julia Blyth (BG 649618).

Sphenophorus venatus (Say, 1831). “‘Nantucket’ (*Dimmock*)” (Johnson 1930).

Sphenophorus zaeae Walsh, 1867. Timothy Billbug. “Maxcys Pond, June 7. Surfside, Aug. 20” (Johnson 1930).

Entiminae (Broad-nosed Weevils)

Aphrastus taeniatus Say, 1831. Larvae develop in roots of grasses. “July 3–Sept. 13. Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*). On hazel” (Johnson 1930, *A. taeniatus* Gyll.).

* *Cyrtepistomus castaneus* (Roelofs, 1873). Asiatic Oak Weevil. Introduced from Asia. Three adults hiding between beaked hazelnut leaves, Squam Swamp, 8/8/2012 (BG 741881).

Otiorhynchus (Dorymerus) sulcatus (Fabricius, 1775). Black Vine Weevil; introduced from Europe. “June 21–Sept. 8. Tuckernuck, July 17 (*Brooks*)” (Johnson 1930, *Brachyrhinus sulcatus* Fab.). 8/4/2012, photographed on the side of a building by Jennifer Forman Orth (BG 734230).

Otiorhynchus (Pendragon) ovatus (Linnaeus, 1758). Strawberry Root Weevil; introduced from Eurasia. “July 17–Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930, *Brachyrhinus ovatus* Linn.).

Sitona lepidus Gyllenhal, 1834. Clover Root Weevil. “Sept. 13–20 (*Henshaw*)” (Johnson 1930, *S. flavescens* Marsh.).

Sitona lineellus (Bonsdorff, 1785). On various legumes. “Aug. 24, 1921” (Johnson 1930, *S. discoidea* Gyll.). *Sitona discoideus* (Gyllenhal, 1834) is an Old World species, and old records from Rhode Island have all proved to refer to *S. lineellus*. Bright’s (1994) distribution map for *S. lineellus* shows a dot on Nantucket.

Hyperinae (Clover and Alfalfa Weevils)

Donus (Antidonus) zoilus (Scopoli, 1763). Clover Leaf Weevil. “Maxcys Pond, Sept. 8. ‘Nantucket’ (*Bolter*)” (Johnson 1930, *Hypera punctata* Fab.).

Hypera maritima (Titus, 1911). “Bathing Beach, June 20. Surfside, July 25 (*Emerton*)” (Johnson 1930, *Phytonomus maritimus* Titus).

Hypera nigrirostris (Fabricius, 1775). Larvae feed on clover and birdsfoot trefoil. “Tuckernuck, Aug. 5 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930, *Phytonomus nigrirostris* Fab.).

Lixinae

Scaphomorphus calandroides (Randall, 1838). On sea rocket. “May 30–Oct. 10” (Johnson 1930, *Cleonus calandroides* Rand.).

Mesoptiliinae

Laemosaccus nephele (Herbst, 1797). “Woods on road to Taupaushaw, July 24, 1928. On oak” (Johnson 1930, *Laemosaccus plagiatus* Fab.).

Molytinae

Conotrachelus nenuphar (Herbst, 1797). Plum Curculio. “June 24, ovipositing in plums. Sept. 13 (*Frost*)” (Johnson 1930).

Pissodes strobi (Peck, 1817). White Pine Weevil. “Woods east side of Hummock Pond, July 21, 1929 (*Emerton*)” (Johnson 1930).

Scolytinae (Bark and Ambrosia Beetles)

Hylastes tenuis Eichhoff, 1868. Mostly on pines. “Fair grounds, June 23” (Johnson 1930, *H. tenuis* Erick.).

HYMENOPTERA (Ants, Bees, Wasps and Sawflies)

Symphyta (Sawflies, Horntails, and Wood Wasps)

(Johnson 1930, pp. 91–93)

CEPHOIDEA

CEPHIDAE

Janus sp. Larvae bore in stems of trees and shrubs. “Maxcys Pond, July 16” (Johnson 1930).

SIRICOIDEA

SIRICIDAE

Sirex edwardsii (Brullé, 1846). Larvae bore in wood of pine trees. “Common, Sept. 14, 1928, on partly dead [pitch] pines destroyed by the Pine tipmoth. Only males were obtained. . . On Sept. 29 Mr. Sanford obtained a section of a tree from which a female emerged Oct. 5. Also common Sept. 11, 1929, but only one small female was taken” (Johnson 1928, 1930).

* *Tremex columba* (Linnaeus, 1763). Adult found squished on sidewalk by Pacific National Bank, 11/2/2019 (MMA); live adult at Lily Pond Park, 9/24/2020 (INAT 69557805).

TENTHREDINOIDEA

ARGIDAE

Arge abdominalis (Leach, 1817). Larvae feed on azalea leaves. “Common, July 27–Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930).

Arge coccinea (Fabricius, 1804). Larvae feed on sumac leaves. “Shawkemo, June 24. Hummock Pond, Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930, *Arge miniata* Klug? var.).

Arge macleayi (Leach, 1817). Larvae have been collected from black cherry leaves on Nantucket (Smith 1989). “Maxcys Pond, June 22 and July 16. Sacacha Pond, Aug. 19” (Johnson 1930).

Arge pectoralis (Leach, 1817). Larvae feed on Betulaceae leaves; hazelnut is presumably the main host on Nantucket. An undetermined *Arge* larva was found feeding on beaked hazelnut at Stump Pond, 9/5/2019 (BG 1723531); others collected on the same host at Stump Pond, 9/25/2020; “Shawkemo, June 24” (Johnson 1930).

* *Arge quidia* D.R. Smith, 1989. Larvae feeding on scrub oak leaves, Tuckernuck, 9/10/2011 (BG 575164); Reyes Pond, 9/5/2019; Squam Swamp, 9/8/2019.

* *Schizocerella pilicornis* (Holmgren, 1868). Larvae mine leaves of purslane; found at Ice Pond Lot, 8/5/2012.

* *Sterictiphora serotina* D.R. Smith, 1969. Young larvae cut characteristic sinusoidal channels into black cherry leaves. Larva collected at State Forest, 6/10/2013, adult emerged April 2014 (BG 920494; USNM; Eiseman 2015b). Larvae probably of this species on black cherry at State Forest, 6/11/2016 and Lost Farm, 6/12/2016.

DIPRIONIDAE

* *Monoctenus* sp. Larvae feed on juniper; one adult male emerged in spring 2015 from soil collected with an arrowwood plant dug from along the Polpis Bike Path in December 2014 (BG 1052805; USNM).

PERGIDAE

* *Acordulecera dorsalis* complex. Reared from larvae found feeding on scrub oak leaves, Squam Swamp, 6/9/2016 (USNM).

TENTHREDINIDAE

Allantinae

Allantus (Emphytus) mellipes (Norton, 1861). Larvae feed on strawberry leaves. “Coleman Bird Sanctuary, June 8” (Johnson 1930).

Ametastegia (Protemphytus) tenera (Fallén, 1808). Larvae feed on *Rumex* leaves. “Fair grounds, June 9. Grove Lane, June 16” (Johnson 1930, *Allantus (Emphytina) vanduzei* Roh.).

Blennocampinae

Eutomostethus ephippium ephippium (Panzer, 1798). Probably introduced from Europe, where the larvae are known to feed on grasses. “Grove Lane, Aug. 9. Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Tomostethus inhabilis* Nort.).

* *Eutomostethus luteiventris* (Klug, 1816). Introduced from Europe; larva mine and bore in rush stems. Larvae at Grove Lane, 6/15/2018.

?*Monophadnus* sp. “Coleman Bird Sanctuary, June 8. Tom Nevers, June 22” (Johnson 1930). Some species formerly placed in *Monophadnus* are now assigned to other genera.

* *Periclista albicollis* (Norton, 1872). Reared from larvae found feeding on black and scrub oak leaves, Squam Swamp and Pout Ponds, 6/9/2016 (USNM).

Dolerinae

Larvae in this subfamily feed on horsetails, grasses, sedges, and rushes. No hosts are recorded for the species found on Nantucket.

Dolerus (Achaetoprion) beauvoisi D.R. Smith, 2009. “Coleman Bird Sanctuary, June 8. Maxcys Pond, June 22. Sacacha Pond, June 24” (Johnson 1930, *Dolerus bicolor* Beauv.).

Dolerus (Loderus) gilvipes albifrons (Norton, 1861). “Maxcys Pond, June 7 and June 22” (Johnson 1930, *Loderus albifrons* Nort.).

Dolerus (Neodolerus) sericeus Say, 1824. “Coleman Bird Sanctuary, June 8. Maxcys Pond, June 8” (Johnson 1930).

Heterarthrinae

Endelomyia aethiops (Gmelin, 1790). Roseslug, Rose Sawfly. Introduced from Eurasia; larvae feed on rose leaves. “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17, 1927” (Johnson 1930, *Caliroa aethiops* Fab.).

* *Fenusa pumila* Leach, 1817. Birch leafminer, introduced from Europe. Larvae on gray birch, Larson Rd. by Milestone Bog, 8/29/2015, adults emerged April 2016 (BG 1295074; USNM); empty mines at Wigwam Ponds, 7/30/2017.

* *Fenusa ulmi* Sundevall, 1847. Elm leafminer, introduced from Europe. Empty mines on American elm found at Lily Pond Park, 7/28/2017.

* *Metallus lanceolatus* (Thomson, 1870). Avens leafminer, introduced from Europe. Larvae on *Geum canadense*, Squam Swamp, 8/8/2012.

Metallus rohweri MacGillivray, 1909. Blackberry Leafminer. “Polpis, Sept. 9” (Johnson 1930); Smith (1971) cites an undated specimen from Sherborn. Leaf mines on *Rubus cuneifolius*, UMass classroom, 9/7/2011; leaf mines on *R. flagellaris*, Coskata Woods, 9/9/2011; leaf mines on blackberry, Coskata Woods and Dead Horse Valley, 8/6/2012; leaf mines on *R. flagellaris*, Trott’s Swamp, 8/28/2015; leaf mines on blackberry, Sanford Farm, 8/28/2015, adult emerged July 2016 (USNM); leaf mines on blackberry, road to Gibbs Pond, 8/29/2015 (Eiseman & Smith 2017).

* *Profenusa lucifex* (Ross, 1936). Larvae mining leaves of scrub oak, 9/5–8/2019, Reyes Pond, Stump Pond, and Squam Swamp.

Nematinae

Cladius (Cladius) pectinicornis (Geoffroy, 1785). Bristly Rose Slug. “Grove Lane, Sept. 8” (Johnson 1930, *C. isomerus* Nort.). D. R. Smith maintains that true *C. pectinicornis* is strictly Palearctic, in which case the correct name for the North American form is *C. difformis* (Panzer, 1799).

* *Craterocercus fraternalis* (Norton, 1872). Larvae feeding on leaves of white oak (*Quercus alba*) at Masquetuck, 6/14/2018; adults emerged the following spring (USNM).

* *Euura* sp. Stem gall on *Salix purpurea* collected at Lily Pond Park on 9/3/2019; adult emerged the following spring (USNM).

Hoplocampa sp. Larvae in this genus feed in apples, cherries, shadbush berries, and other rosaceous fruits. “Grove Lane, June 21, 1927” (Johnson 1930).

Pachynematus corniger (Norton, 1861). Larvae feed on *Carex*. “Maxcys Pond, June 22 and Sept. 8. Taupaushaw, June 24” (Johnson 1930).

Pontania (Eupontania) salicispomum (Walsh, 1866). “Forming red galls on the leaves of *Salix discolor*” (Johnson 1930, *P. pomum* Walsh). Galls possibly of this species were found at Grove Lane on 6/15/2018; hairy leaf galls of an undetermined *Pontania* species were found on dwarf prairie willow at Smooth Hummocks, 6/14/2018.

* *Pseudodineura parva* (Norton, 1867). Larvae mine leaves of wood anemone. Larvae or leaf mines found at Squam Swamp and Squam Farm, 5/17/2012; Coskata Woods, 5/18/2012; Masquetuck, 6/11/2013.

Selandriinae

Aneugmenus flavipes (Norton, 1861). Larvae feed on bracken fern. “Polpis, July 27” (Johnson 1930, *Polyselandria flavipes* Nort.); Coskata Woods, 5/18/2012 (BG 644022).

Strongylogaster tacita (Norton, 1860). Adults have been collected from bracken fern. “Maxcys Pond, July 24” (Johnson 1930, *S. tacitus* Say).

Tenthredininae

Macrophya formosa (Klug, 1817). “Fair grounds, June 23. Polpis, June 25. Maxcys Pond, July 16” (Johnson 1930).

Macrophya intermedia (Norton, 1860). “Maxcys Pond, June 25. Taupaushaw, June 24” (Johnson 1930).

Macrophya succincta Cresson, 1880. “Fair grounds, June 9–23. Hummock Pond, June 22. July 4 (*Cushman*)” (Johnson 1930).

Tenthredo basilaris Say, 1824. “Hummock Pond, Aug. 18. Surfside, Aug. 20. Sacacha Pond, Sept. 10 (*Sanford*)” (Johnson 1930).

Tenthredo verticalis Say, 1824. “Maxcys Pond, July 16” (Johnson 1930, *Tenthredella verticallis* Say).

Parasitica (Parasitic Wasps)

(Johnson 1930, pp. 93–110)

ICHNEUMONOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, pp. 93–107)

PROCTOTRUPOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, p. 107)

DIAPRIOIDEA

DIAPRIIDAE

* *Trichopria* sp. Found on *Iva frutescens*, Masquetuck, 7/28/2017 (BG 1462400; CSE).

CHALCIDOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, pp. 108–110)

CHALCIDIDAE

Brachymeria compsilurae (Crawford, 1911). “July 16–Sept. 16” (Johnson 1930).

Chalcis barbara (Cresson, 1872). “Maxcys Pond, June 21 (Emerton). Tuckernuck, June 21 (Allen)” (Johnson 1930, *Smicra rufofemorata* Cress.).

Chalcis flebilis (Cresson, 1872). “June 27–Aug. 21. Tuckernuck, July 21 (Allen). Muskeget, June 14 (Brooks)” (Johnson 1930, *Smicra flebilis* Cress.).

Conura albifrons (Walsh, 1861). “Fair grounds, Aug. 18” (Johnson 1930, *Spilochalcis albifrons* Walsh).

Conura maria (Riley, 1870). A parasitoid of giant silk moths (Saturniidae). “Maxcys Pond, Aug. 7” (Johnson 1930, *Spilochalcis mariae* Riley).

Conura nigricornis (Fabricius, 1798). “Common, Aug. 8–Sept. 16” (Johnson 1930, *Smicra braccata* Sanb.).

Conura torvina (Cresson, 1872). “Fair grounds, Aug. 8. Maxcys Pond, Sept. 13” (Johnson 1930, *Smicra torvina*).

Haltichella rhyacioniae Gahan, 1927. “‘Nantucket, 1882’ (Scudder). Reared from pine tip moth” (Johnson 1930).

ENCYRTIDAE

Aenasius pergandei (Howard, 1895). “Surfside, Sept. 16, 1927” (Johnson 1930, *Chalcaspis pergandei* How.).

* *Ageniaspis* sp. Emerged 7/7/2016 from cocoon of *Marmara viburnella* collected at corner of Turner & Milestone, 6/11/2016 (Eiseman et al. 2017; EME)

* *Ageniaspis bicoloripes* (Girault, 1915). Emerged 8/8/2012 from *Phyllonorycter* mine on scrub oak collected at Madequecham, 8/3/2012 (BG 741926; EME); emerged 8/8/2014 from *Cameraria quercivorella* mine collected at Tawpeshaw, 7/25/2014 (BG 1022952; EME); emerged 8/10–20/2014 from mines of *Phyllonorycter rileyella* collected at Milestone Cranberry Bog, 7/25/2014 (BG 1023490; EME).

* *Copidosoma* sp. Emerged 9/3/2017 from a larva of *Strepsicrates smithiana* collected at LLNF (BG 1486455).

* *Encyrtus* sp. Emerged 4/13/2015 from *Viburnum dentatum* plant dug from Polpis Bike Path in Dec. 2014 (BG 1152238; EME).

Ooencyrtus kuvanae (Howard, 1910). “‘Nantucket, Dec. 1917’ (Gipsy Moth Lab.). An introduced egg parasite of the gipsy moth” (Johnson 1930).

EULOPHIDAE

[See Appendix 1 for new records of Eulophidae reared from galls and leaf mines]

* *Dicladocerus* sp. Reared from *Coleophora* larval cases collected at Pout Ponds on 7/30/2017 (BMNH).

* *Euderus albitarsis* (Zetterstedt, 1838). Reared from *Coleophora* larval cases collected at Pout Ponds on 7/30/2017 (BMNH).

Euplectrus bicolor (Swederus, 1795). “Polpis, Sept. 11, 1929” (Johnson 1930).

* *Sympiesis* possible n. sp. Reared from leaf-tying larva of *Strepsicrates smithiana* on bayberry collected at Linda Loring Nature Foundation on 7/27/2017 (BMNH).

Tetrastichus cuproideus Howard, 1897. “Maxcys Pond, July 26” (Johnson 1930, *Pteromalus cuproides* How.).

Tetrastichinae sp. Forty-four specimens emerged in spring 2020 from the cocoon of an *Arge* larva collected at Stump Pond on 9/5/2019 (CSE).

EUPELMIDAE

* *Brasema gemmarii* (Ashmead, 1886). Emerged 9/9/2012 from *Quercus prinoides* leaf galls collected in eastern moors, 8/4/2012 (BG 734521; CNC).

Eupelmus sp. “June 2. From pine tips” (Johnson 1930).

* *Eupelmus dryorhizoxeni* Ashmead, 1886. Gibson (2011) lists a female specimen (USNM) from Nantucket collected by J. H. Emerton on June 21 (year not recorded).

* *Eupelmus messene* Walker, 1839. Emerged 8/27/2012 from *Calycomyza solidaginis* leaf mine collected at Ice Pond Lot, 8/5/2012 (BG 743747); emerged 5/22/2014 from *Diastrophus* gall collected at Pout Ponds; emerged 8/6/2014 from *Diplolepis* rose gall collected at Norwood Farm, 7/26/2014.

EURYTOMIDAE

Eurytoma sp. “The Creeks, June 23” (Johnson 1930); reared from *Euura* gall on *Salix purpurea* collected at Lily Pond Park on 9/3/2019 (CSE; INAT 47227816).

Eurytoma nr. *pachyneuron* Girault, 1916. “Sacacha Pond, July 19” (Johnson 1930, *E.* sp. near *pater* Gir.).

* *Rileya* sp. Reared from an *Asphondylia* gall on seaside goldenrod collected at Madaket on 9/8/2011 (BG 591865).

* *Sycophila* spp. Emerged 9/20/2011 from *Philonix nigra* gall collected at Coskata Pond, 9/20/2011 (BG 595313); emerged from gall on *Quercus prinoides* collected at eastern moors, 8/4/2012 (BG 743832).

Tetramesa sp. “Maxcys Pond, June 25” (Johnson 1930, *Harmolita* sp.).

LEUCOSPIDAE

Leucospis affinis Say, 1824. “Taupaushaw, July 25” (Johnson 1930).

MYMARIDAE

* *Ooctonus* sp. Emerged 8/26/2012 from a sprig of bearberry (*Arctostaphylos uva-ursi*) with galls of *Tamalia coweni* (Aphididae) (BG 743724; CNC). As far as is known, species in this genus are parasitoids of spittlebug eggs.

ORMYRIDAE

[See Appendix 1 for new Ormyridae records]

PERILAMPIDAE

Perilampus chrysopae Crawford, 1914. “Fair grounds, Aug. 8, 1918” (Johnson 1930).

Perilampus fulvicornis Ashmead, 1886. “Fair grounds, July 17. Muskeget, July 14 (Brooks)” (Johnson 1930).

Perilampus platigaster Say, 1836. Emerged 9/5–12/2017 from cocoons of *Microgaster* parasitizing a leaf-rolling moth on bugleweed (*Lycopus*), Stump Pond, 7/30/2017 (BG 1486459; ROM); “Maxcys Pond, July 21” (Johnson 1930, *P. platygaster* Say).

PTEROMALIDAE

[See Appendix 1 for new Pteromalidae records]

Catolaccus aeneoviridis (Girault, 1911). “Polpis, July 25” (Johnson 1930, *C. aeneaviridis* Gir.).

Lycrus sp. “Polpis, Sept. 11, 1929” (Johnson 1930, *Zatropis* sp.).

Neocatolaccus tylodermae (Ashmead, 1893). “Muskeget, June 14 (Brooks)” (Johnson 1930, *N. tylodermatis* Ashm.).

Pteromalus spp. “Maxcys Pond, June 25, 1926; Polpis, June 25, 1928” (Johnson 1930, *Habrocytus* spp.).

Trichomalopsis sp. “Hummock Pond, Sept. 10” (Johnson 1930, *Eupteromalus* sp.).

Urolepis singularis (Ashmead, 1896). “Maxcys Pond, June 24” (Johnson 1930, *Belonura singularis* Ashm.).

TORYMIDAE

[See Appendix 1 for records of undetermined Torymidae]

Torymus tubicola (Osten Sacken, 1870). Emerged 4/18/2012 from *Amphibolips* gall collected 9/2011 (BG 731718); “Bred from oak galls, July 3” (Johnson 1930, *Syntomaspis tubicola* O. S.).

PLATYGASTROIDEA

[See Appendix 1 for records of Platygastriidae reared from galls]

CYNIPOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, pp. 107–108)

EVANIOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, p. 107)

LEPIDOPTERA (Moths and Butterflies)

GELECHIOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, pp. 71–72; Jones & Kimball 1943, pp. 168–180, 183, 184–5)

[See Appendix 1 for additional new records of leaf-mining and gall-inducing Gelechioidea.]

AUTOSTICHIDAE

Glyphidocera meyrickella Busck, 1907. “Fairly common. July 15–26” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Glyphidocera septentrionella Busck, 1904. “Polpis, July 12, 1941 (3). Probably not rare” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *G. speratella* Busck).

BATRACHEDRIDAE

Batrachedra ?salicipomonella Clemens, 1865. “In A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

BLASTOBASIDAE

Asaphocrita ?aphidiella (Walsingham, 1907). “Waq., Aug. 16. 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Holcocera nr. confluentella* Dietz).

Calosima melanostriatella (Dietz, 1910). “Sea shore, July 26, 1940 (J. M. Andrews)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Holcocera melanostriatella* Dietz).

Holcocera ?chalcfrontella Clemens, 1863. “Polpis, June 20, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *H. nr. maligemmella* Murt.).

Pigritia ?laticapitella Clemens, 1860. “Sea shore, July 27, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *P. ?angustipennella* Dietz).

COLEOPHORIDAE

Coleophora atromarginata Braun, 1914. A pistol casebearer. Larva on white oak, Lost Farm, 6/12/2016, adult emerged 7/4/2016 (CNC); “Polpis, Aug. 1, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Coleophora limosipennella (Duponchel, 1843). “Larval cases abundant on planted elms, Town; adults emerged, July 28–Aug. 10” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Coleophora mayrella (Hübner, 1813). “In A. Bolter coll. (as *fabricella* Zell.)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *C. coruscipennella* Clem.).

Coleophora multipulvella Chambers, 1878. “Pistol Case-bearer. June 22. Larval cases on beach plum” (Johnson 1930, *C. malivorella* Riley); “Larval cases sometimes plentiful on beach plum. Adult emerged, July 15, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *C. atlantica* Heinr.).

* *Coleophora rosacella* Clemens, 1864. Coskata Woods; Squam Swamp (CNC; BG 872951, BG 1035035).

* *Coleophora rupestrella* McDunnough, 1955. Madequecham (CNC; BG 1035047).

COSMOPTERIGIDAE

* *Cosmopterix scirpicola* Hodges, 1962. Stem miner of *Schoenoplectus* spp. UMass field station, 8/29/2015, 9/8/2019; Masquetuck, 7/28/2017, 9/7/2019.

Limnaecia phragmitella Stainton, 1851. Larvae develop in cattail seedheads. “Waq. and sea shore, infrequent. July 9–Aug. 12” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Stigmatophora sexnotella (Chambers, 1878). Forms galls in stems of blue curls (*Trichostema*). “Waq., July 2, 1936; July 19, 1937” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

* *Stilbosis* sp. Leaf mines on scrub oak, Squam Farm, 8/27/2015; Stump Pond, 9/5/2019; Masquetuck, 9/7/2019; Squam Swamp, 9/8/2019.

DEPRESSARIIDAE

Agonopterix lythrella (Walsingham, 1889). “Polpis, Aug. 16, 1939; bred from *Hypericum virginicum*, Aug. 14, 1941. The larvae press together the top leaves of the foodplant, and are abundant” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *A. arcuella* Clarke).

Agonopterix robiniella (Packard, 1869). “Aug. 5, at light. Larva feeds on locust, folding the leaf lengthwise” (Johnson 1930); “Larvae common, but adults rarely taken. July 9–Aug. 5” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Agonopterix thelmae Clarke, 1941. “Pine woods, May 12, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Agonopterix walsinghamella (Busck, 1902). “Quite common. More commonly in Sept. and Oct., but taken in nearly every month of the year” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *A. fernaldella* Wlshm.).

Antaeotricha leucillana Zeller, 1854. “Common. May 4–June 5; July 28–Aug. 8” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Stenoma algidella* Wlk.).

Antaeotricha unipunctella (Clemens, 1863). “Waq., Aug. 12, 1936; scrub oak region, Aug. 9, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Stenoma unipunctella* Clem.).

Depressaria cinereocostella Clemens, 1864. “Waq., Sept. 22, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Depressaria radiella (Goeze, 1783). “Waq., at bait, Apr. 28, 1936; Wauwinet, at light, Sept. 4, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *D. heracliiana* DeGeer).

Gonioterma mistrella (Busck, 1907). “Bathing Beach, Sept. 4, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1932, *Stenoma mistrella* Busck).

Machimia tentoriferella Clemens, 1860. “Polpis, Sept. 13. Larva on oak, plum, etc.” (Johnson 1930, *Cryptolechia tentoriferella* Clem.); “Well distributed but infrequent. Sept. 1–Oct. 6” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

* *Menesta melanella* Murtfeldt, 1890. Larva on scrub oak, 9/12/2011 (BG 1040130).

Psilocorsis cryptolechiella (Chambers, 1872). “Waq., June 4, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Cryptolechia obsoletella* Zell.).

Psilocorsis quercicella Clemens, 1860. Reared from scrub oak, State Forest (CNC). “Polpis, July 9, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Cryptolechia quercicella* Clem.).

Rectiostoma xanthobasis (Zeller, 1875). “Scrub oak region, not rare. July 11” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Setiostoma xanthobasis* Zell.).

ELACHISTIDAE

Blastodacna bicristatella (Chambers, 1875). “Waq., May 23, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *B. ?curvilineella* Cham.).

Elachista ?cucullata Braun, 1921. “Polpis, June 17, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Elachista ?illectella (Clemens, 1860). “Polpis, May 5, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *E. nr. praematurella* Clem.).

Elachista ?orestella Busck, 1908. “Waq., June 1, 1942” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

GELECHIIDAE

Anacampsis conclusella (Walker, 1864). “Waq., July 11, 1941; Polpis, July 12, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Anacampsis innocuella (Zeller, 1873). “Larvae common on *Populus alba*, 1942; adults bred, July 3 and 5” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Aristotelia roseosuffusella (Clemens, 1860). Reared from *Tephrosia virginiana*, Lost Farm (CNC; BG 1633845). “Polpis, June 30, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Aristotelia rubidella (Clemens, 1860). “Polpis, July 12, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Aroga compositella (Walker, 1864). “Waq., July 19 and 28, 1937” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Gelechia coloradensis* Busck).

Aroga trialbamaculella (Chambers, 1875). Red-striped Fireworm. “Swampy regions. June 5, 1936; May 27, 1941; July 22, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Gelechia trialbamaculella* Cham.).

Battaristis ?vittella (Busck, 1916). “Waq., July 21, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Duvita ?vittella* Busck).

Chionodes arenella (Forbes, 1922). “Sea shore and Waq., not rare. Aug. 12–Sept. 20” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Gelechia arenella* Forbes).

Chionodes bicostomaculella (Chambers, 1872). “July 14” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Telphusa bicostomaculella* Cham.).

Chionodes discoocellella (Chambers, 1872). “Town, Oct. 2, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Gelechia discoocellella* Cham.).

Chionodes formosella (Murtfeldt, 1881). “Swamp area, July 9, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Gelechia vernella* Murt.).

Chionodes mediofuscella (Clemens, 1863). “Not uncommon. May 19–June 21; one, Aug. 27, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Gelechia mediofuscella* Clem.).

Coleotechnites quercivorella (Chambers, 1872). “Polpis, May 24, 1936; May 27, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Recurvaria quercivorella* Cham.).

Dichomeris bipunctellus (Walsingham, 1882). “Maxcys Pond, Aug. 18, 1926” (Johnson 1930); “Common. Apr. 18–May 14; Aug. 18; Oct. 14–22” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Dichomeris levisella (Fyles, 1904). “Sea shore, July 26, 1940 (J. M. Andrews)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Trichotaphe levisella* Fyles).

Dichomeris ligulella Hübner, 1818. Reared from larva on scrub oak, Squam Farm, 6/25/2013, adult 7/9/2013 (BG 870666). “Abundant in 1941. May 18–Aug. 5” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Dichomeris punctipennella Clemens, 1860. “Polpis and Waq. Rare. July 9–17” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Dichomeris serrativittella (Zeller, 1873). “Sea shore, July 29, 1940 (J. M. Andrews)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Trichotaphe serrativittella* Zell.).

Dichomeris ventrellus (Fitch, 1854). “Waq., and scrub oak region near shore; rare. May 16; Oct. 14–24” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Exoteleia pinifoliella (Chambers, 1880). Pine Needleminer Moth. Mining pitch pine, Gardner Farm, 6/20/2013 (BG 1073601). “In A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Filatima serotinella (Busck, 1903). “Polpis, May 24, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Gelechia serotinella* Busck).

“*Gelechia* n. sp. (Clarke MS.). Waq. and scrub oak area, not rare. Aug. 9–29 . . . The larvae inhabit tortuous sand-tubes, on sand beneath mats of *Hudsonia*; pupation in a sand-grain cocoon” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Glauce pectenalaella Chambers, 1875. “Polpis, June 17, 1936; July 9, 1940; July 12, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Gnorimoschema banksiella Busck, 1903. “Waq. and Polpis, rare. June 10–30” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Gnorimoschema salinaris Busck, 1911. “Wauwinet, Sept. 10, 1940, from pupa. Galls fairly common in *Solidago sempervirens*, but only on the beaches from Wauwinet to Great Point” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Metzneria lappella (Linnaeus, 1758). Burdock Seedhead Moth. “Aug. 5, at light” (Johnson 1930); “Occasional, in diverse localities. June 5–Aug. 10” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

* *Monochroa* sp. Reared from leaf mines on *Scirpus*, Head of Hummock Pond (CNC).

Neotelphusa ?praefixa (Braun, 1921). “Waq., June 30, 1941 (3); June 30, 1942” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Telphusa ?praefixa* Braun).

Pseudotelphusa fuscopunctella (Clemens, 1863). “Common. July 9–29” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Telphusa fuscopunctella* Clem.).

Pseudotelphusa palliderosacella (Chambers, 1878). “Swamp area, rare. May 27–July 17” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Telphusa palliderosacella* Cham.).

* *Pseudotelphusa quercinigracella* (Chambers, 1872). Reared from scrub oak, Milestone Cranberry Bog & State Forest (CNC; BG 899472, BG 1156989).

Pseudotelphusa sp. Reared from scrub oak, Milestone Cranberry Bog (CNC; BG 1030657).

Scrobipalpa atriplicella (von Röslerstamm, 1839). “Waq., June 10, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Phthorimaea chenopodiella* Busck).

* “*Taygete*” *sylvicolella* (Busck, 1903). Reared from gall of *Callirhytis quercusventricosa* on scrub oak, Squam Swamp, collected 6/9/2016, emerged 7/8/2016 (BG 1311044).

Telphusa longifasciella (Clemens, 1863). “Well distributed but infrequent. May 16–23” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

MOMPHIDAE

Mompha circumscriptella (Zeller, 1873). Kelly Omand reared adults from evening primrose seed capsules collected in the NCF community garden at Tupancy Links, November 2020; “Waq., infrequent. June 4–July 13” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Mompha eloisella (Clemens, 1860). Larvae bore in stems of evening primrose. “Waq., not rare. July 17–Aug. 6” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Cyphophora eloisella* Clem.).

Mompha stellella Busck, 1906. “Waq., and Polpis, usually in house, and not rare. Feb. 22–May 26; Oct. 10–Nov. 19” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Mompha n. sp. “Waq., June 4, 1936 (8)” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

SCYTHRIDIDAE

Scythris basilaris (Zeller, 1855). “In A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Scythris eboracensis (Zeller, 1855). “Waq., June 24, 1942 (2)” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

STATHMOPODIDAE

* *Stathmopoda aenea* (Braun, 1918). Larvae on New York fern, Stump Pond, 9/5/2019.

YPONOMEUTOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, p. 72; Jones & Kimball 1943, pp. 180–183)

[See Appendix 1 for additional new records of leaf-mining Yponomeutoidea.]

ARGYRESTHIIDAE (Shiny Head-standing Moths)

(Jones & Kimball 1943, p. 182)

Argyresthia alternatella Kearfott, 1908. Larvae feed in juniper berries. “Waq., Apr. 4 and May 10, 1939; June 2, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Argyresthia oreasella Chambers, 1877. Larvae bore in shoots of *Prunus* and *Amelanchier*. “Swamp, July 17, 1941; Waq., June 30, 1942” (Jones & Kimball 1943); adult collected at State Forest, 7/27/2014 (CNC; BG 1018430).

ATTEVIDAE (Tropical Ermine Moths)
(Johnson 1930, p. 72)

Atteva aurea (Fitch, 1856). *Ailanthus* webworm moth. “Maxcys Pond, July 26. Old North Cemetery, Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930, *A. punctella* Cram.); “More widely distributed than its recorded foodplant, *Ailanthus*. Infrequent, July 26–Sept. 14” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

GLYPHIPTERIGIDAE (Sedge and False Diamondback Moths)
(Jones & Kimball 1943, p. 182)

* *Acrolepiopsis heppneri* Gaedike, 1984. Larvae window-feeding on leaves of *Smilax rotundifolia*, Almanac Pond Rd., 9/24/2020, adults emerged 10/13–10/25/2020 (CSE).

Acrolepiopsis incertella (Chambers, 1872). “Polpis, May 5, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Acrolepia incertella* Cham.). The larva of this species feeds as a leaf-tier on *Smilax* in spring; this record requires verification since the adult is very similar to that of *A. heppneri*.

PLUTELLIDAE (Diamondback Moths)
(Jones & Kimball 1943, p. 182)

Plutella xylostella (Linnaeus, 1758). Larvae feed on *Brassica* spp. and other mustards, as leafminers in the first instar and later externally. “Sometimes quite common. May 27–Sept. 9” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *P. maculipennis* Curt.).

TORTRICOIDEA

TORTRICIDAE (Leafroller Moths)
(Johnson 1930, pp. 72–74; Jones & Kimball 1943, pp. 148–167)

Acleris spp. – “Knowledge of this genus is incomplete, and a future revision will make changes in the present conception of species. The material studied indicates the presence of several additional species for the two islands [Nantucket and Martha’s Vineyard]” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Acleris albicomana (Clemens, 1865). “Maxcys Pond, July 16. The larva feeds on rose, etc.” (Johnson 1930, *Argyrotoxa albicomana* Clem.); “Fairly common. July 3–18” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Argyrotoxa albicomana* Clem.).

Acleris flavivittana (Clemens, 1864). “Waq., Dec. 20, 1940; Nov. 14, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Peronea flavivittana* Clem.).

Acleris maccana (Treitschke, 1835). “Oak woods, at bait. Oct. 7, 1939” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Peronea maccana* Tr.).

Acleris maculidorsana (Clemens, 1864). “Polpis, Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930, *Peronea maculidorsana*); “Waq., Apr. 7, 1940 (2)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *P. maculidorsana* Clem.).

Acleris minuta (Robinson, 1869). Yellowheaded fireworm moth. “Reported from the cranberry bogs” (Johnson 1930, *Peronea minuta* var. *cinderella* Riley); “Generally distributed, rather infrequent. Apr. 5–July 7; Dec. 6, 1941 (2)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *P. minuta* Rob. Form *cinderella* Riley).

* *Acleris robinsoniana* (Forbes, 1923). Reared from *Rosa virginiana*, Gardner Farm, 6/13/2013, adult 7/11/2013 (CNC; BG 873685).

Acleris schalleriana (Linnaeus, 1761). “Waq., Oct. 7, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Peronea schalleriana* Linn.).

Acleris ?semiannula (Robinson, 1869). “Waq., July 6, 1939” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Peronea ?semiannula* Rob.).

Aethes ?angulatana (Robinson, 1869). “Sea shore, Aug. 27 (2) and Sept. 20, 1940. (Identified with “?”)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Phalonia angulatana* Rob.).

Aethes atomosana (Busck, 1907). “Waq., rare. Aug. 18–Sept. 11” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Phalonia atomosana* Busck).

Amorbia humerosana Clemens, 1860. “Polpis, locally abundant. June 17–July 11” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Ancylis burgessiana (Zeller, 1875). “Polpis, June 20, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera burgessiana* Zell.).

Ancylis comptana (Frölich, 1828). Strawberry leafroller moth. “Common. May 5–Aug. 8” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera comptana* Froh.).

Ancylis floridana (Zeller, 1875). Larvae tie bearberry leaves, pupating between them. “Common. May 16–Aug. 6” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera floridana* Zell.).

Ancylis goodelliana (Fernald, 1882). “Polpis, May 20, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera goodelliana* Fern.).

Ancylis laciniana (Zeller, 1875). “In A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera laciniana* Zell.).

Ancylis maritima Dyar, 1904. “Beach pea heavily infested, July” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera maritima* Dyar).

Ancylis metamelana (Walker, 1863). “Well distributed but infrequent. June 8–July 9” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera angulifasciana* Zell.).

Ancylis ?mira Heinrich, 1929. At light, 8/6/2012 (BG 694239); reared from larva folding swamp azalea leaves, Stump Pond, 7/30/2017, adult 8/24/2017 (BG 1462651, CSE).

Ancylis nubeculana (Clemens, 1860). “Polpis, and Thorn Lot; infrequent. June 7–July 12” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera nubeculana* Clem.).

Ancylis spiraefoliata complex. Reared from scrub oak, State Forest, 8/8/2012 (BG 1034632; CUIC). This complex includes *A. burgessiana*, *A. fuscociliana*, *A. laciniana*, and *A. spiraefoliata*. Jason Dombroskie reported that the specimen is intermediate between two of these “species.” “Polpis, May 29, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera ?spiraefoliata* Clem.).

Ancylis nr. semiovana (Zeller, 1875). “Waq., June 19, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera nr. semiovana* Zell.).

Ancylis subaequana (Zeller, 1875). “Taupaushaw, June 24” (Johnson 1930, *Anchylopera subaequana* Zell.); “Well distributed but infrequent. June 8–July 10” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Anchylopera subaequana* Zell.).

Anopina ednana (Kearfott, 1907). “Waq., July 6, 1940; July 10, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Cnephasia ednana* Kft.).

Apotomis albeolana (Zeller, 1875). “Waq., June 15, 1937” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Aphania albeolana* Zell.).

Apotomis deceptana (Kearfott, 1905). “Waq., Aug. 7, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Aphania deceptana* Kft.).

Archips argyrospila (Walker, 1863). Fruit tree leafroller moth. Dead Horse Valley, 7/26/2017 (BG 1461473); “July 16–21. Larva on apple and plum” (Johnson 1930); “Common and variable. July 5–21” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Archips fervidana (Clemens, 1860). Oak webworm. “Aug. 20. The larvae form large webs on the scrub oak” (Johnson 1930); “Scrub oak region, fairly common. July 10–Aug. 22” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Archips purpurana (Clemens, 1865). “Waq., July 16, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Argyrotaenia pinatubana (Kearfott, 1905). “Waq., May 21, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Argyrotaenia quadrifasciana (Fernald, 1882). “Waq., July 10 and Aug. 9, 1936; July 19, 1937” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

* *Argyrotaenia tabulana* Freeman, 1944. Jack pine tube moth. At light, 8/6/2012 (BG 747079).

Argyrotaenia velutinana (Walker, 1863). Reared from larvae collected 6/14/2018 on marsh elder (*Iva frutescens*) at Masquetuck and greenbriar (*Smilax*) west of Sesachacha Pond (CUIC); “Very common. Apr. 19–Aug. 28; one in house, Jan. 14, 1942” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Capua semifera (Walker, 1863). “Polpis, July 9, 1940 (7)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Archips semifera* Wlk.).

Catastega aceriella Clemens, 1861. Larval feeding sign on red maple at Squam Swamp, 9/7/2011; “General and common. May 24–June 19” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Epinotia aceriella* Clem.).

Catastega timidella Clemens, 1861. Larval feeding sign on scrub oak at Madequecham, 9/8/2011; at Linda Loring Nature Foundation, 8/28/2015; at water tower, 8/29/2015; “Polpis, May 26–June 20; common” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Epinotia timidella* Clem.).

Celypha cespitana (Hübner, 1814). “Waq., July 20, 1939; July 18, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Olethreutes cespitana* Hbn.).

Cenopis karacana Kearfott, 1907. “Scrub oak area, Aug. 9, 1940 (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Sparganothis karacana* Kft.).

Choristoneura fractivittana (Clemens, 1865). “In A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Archips fractivittana* Clem.).

Choristoneura fumiferana (Clemens, 1865). Spruce budworm. “(Miss Hussey collection). This may have been obtained when this moth was so prevalent in 1912 and 1913” (Johnson 1930, *Harmologa fumiferana* Clem.); “In A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *A. fumiferana* Clem.).

Choristoneura obsoletana (Walker, 1863). At light, 8/6/2012 (BG 715917); “Waq., and Wyer’s Valley, infrequent. July 2–27” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Archips obsoletana* Wlk.).

Choristoneura parallela (Robinson, 1869). “Taupaushaw, July 25. Larva on cranberry” (Johnson 1930, *Archips parallela* Rob.); “Waq., and Polpis; not rare. July 9–Sept. 11” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *A. parallela* Rob.).

Choristoneura rosaceana (Harris, 1841). Oblique-banded leafroller. “Common, July 14–Sept. 13. Larva feeds on various trees and shrubs” (Johnson 1930, *Archips rosaceana*); “Waq., common. June 30–Sept. 13” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *A. rosaceana* Harr.).

Clepsis clemensiana (Fernald, 1879). “Maxcys Pond, June 25. Taupaushaw, Aug. 17. Larva feeds on *Solidago*” (Johnson 1930, *Tortrix clemensiana* Fern.); “Fairly common. July 9–Sept. 4” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *T. clemensiana* Fern.).

Clepsis peritana (Clemens, 1860). “Common. June 5–Aug. 7” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Tortrix peritana* Clem.).

Clepsis persicana (Fitch, 1856). “Waq., June 30, July 2 and 7, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Archips persicana* Fitch).

Clepsis virescana (Clemens, 1865). “Open moorlands, May 3, 1937” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Tortrix virescana* Clem.).

Coelostathma discopunctana Clemens, 1860. “Polpis, July 9, 1940; Waq., July 27, 1940; July 17, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Cudonigera houstonana (Grote, 1873). “Waq., at light. July 31, 1937 (2); also by Miss Hussey” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Archips houstonana* Grt.).

Cydia pomonella (Linnaeus, 1758). Codling moth. “Town, Mch. 14 and July 21, 1941 (Miss Harwood)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Carpocapsa pomonella* Linn.).

Ecdytolopha insiticiiana Zeller, 1875. Locust twig borer moth (forms galls on black locust). “Sept. 11” (Johnson 1930); “Adult, Sept. 4, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Endothenia hebesana (Walker, 1863). “Fairly common. June 4–Sept. 4” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Endothenia nubilana (Clemens, 1865). “Waq., June 4 and Aug. 1, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *E. antiquana* Hbn., var. *nubilana* Clem.).

Epiblema brightonana (Kearfott, 1907). “Waq., Aug. 1, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Epiblema exacerbatricana Heinrich, 1923. “Waq., May 23–Sept. 11” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

* *Epiblema otiosana* (Clemens, 1860). Bidens borer moth. Milestone cranberry bog, emerged 8/9/2012 from *Bidens* stem collected 8/4/2012 (BG 687601).

Epiblema resumptana (Walker, 1863). “Waq., June 4, 1942” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *E. abbreviatana* Wlsh.).

Epiblema strenuana (Walker, 1863). “Waq., Aug. 10 and 27, 1939” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Epinotia nr. nisella (Clerck, 1759). “In A. Bolter coll. (var. not stated.)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, listed under *E. nisella* Clerck, form *criddleana* Kft., which is a synonym of *E. cinereana* (Haworth, 1811)).

Epinotia septemberana Kearfott, 1907. “Polpis, Sept. 1, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Epinotia transmissana (Walker, 1863). “Fairly common. May 7–June 24” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Episimus argutana (Clemens, 1860). Leafroller of sumac and witch hazel. “Polpis, and Waq., rare. May 23–July 28” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Eucosma annetteana (Kearfott, 1907). “Waq., and Wyr’s Valley, rare. May 10–Aug. 27” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia annetteana* Kft.).

* *Eucosma baggetti* Wright & Gilligan, 2019. Squam Swamp, 6/12/2013 (BG 859527).

Eucosma clavana (Fernald, 1882). “Waq., Aug. 29, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia clavana* Fern.).

Eucosma ochrocephala (Walsingham, 1895). “Common. Aug. 17–Sept. 20” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia imbridana* Fern.).

Eucosma ochroterminana (Kearfott, 1907). “Widely distributed but infrequent. Aug. 10–Sept. 15” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia ochroterminata* Kft.).

Eucosma olivaceana (Riley, 1881). “Fairly common. June 21–Aug. 2” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia olivaceana* Riley).

Eucosma parmatana (Clemens, 1860). “Quite common. June 23–Sept. 20” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia crispata* Clem.); “Waq., Aug. 5, 1936; Aug. 16, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia alterana* Heinr.).

Eucosma raracana (Kearfott, 1907). “Waq., and sea shore; rare. July 27–Aug. 17” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia raracana* Kft.).

Eucosma refusana (Walker, 1863). “Waq., infrequent. May 3–25” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia refusana* Wlk.).

Eucosma striatana (Clemens, 1860). “Waq., and sea shore; sometimes numerous. July 27–29; Waq., May 27, 1938” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia striatana* Clem.).

Eucosma verniochreana (Heinrich, 1923). “Found infrequently near sea shore. Aug. 10–Sept. 5” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Thiodia verniochreana* Heinr.).

Eumarozia malachitana (Zeller, 1875). “Waq., at bait; Oct. 27, 1937 (2); Sept. 7, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Grapholita interstinctana (Clemens, 1860). Clover head caterpillar moth. “Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930, *Laspeyresia interstinctana* Clem.); “also in A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Grapholita nr. libertina (Heinrich, 1926). “Waq., May 21, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Grapholitha nr. libertina* Heinr.).

Grapholita packardi (Zeller, 1875). “Generally distributed but rare. May 23–July 27” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Grapholitha packardi* Zell.).

* *Grapholita prunivora* (Walsh, 1868). Lesser appleworm moth. Lost Farm, 6/12/2016 (BG 1302987); Grove Lane, south of No Bottom Pond, 7/31/2017 (BG 1462161).

Gymnandrosoma punctidiscanum Dyar, 1904. “Polpis, infrequent. June 20–Aug. 1” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

* *Gynnidomorpha romonana* (Kearfott, 1907). Leaf mines on sea lavender, Masquetuck, 6/11/2013 (Eiseman & Jensen 2015).

Gypsonoma haimbachiana (Kearfott, 1907). Cottonwood twig borer (on various poplars). “Maxcys Pond, June 22. Sacacha Pond, July 19” (Johnson 1930); “Well distributed but infrequent. June 22–Sept. 2” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Gypsonoma salicicolana (Clemens, 1864). “Ident. by dissection, U.S.N.M. (C. Heinrich)” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Hedya ochroleucana (Frölich, 1828). “Sacacha Pond, July 19. Larva on rose” (Johnson 1930, *Olethreutes nimbatana* Clem.); “Waq., and Polpis, rare. June 28–Aug. 10” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Hedia ochroleucana* Hbn.).

Henricus contrastana (Kearfott, 1907). “Polpis, June 21, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Commophila contrastana* Kft.).

Hulda impudens (Walsingham, 1884). “Well distributed, not rare. June 20–July 17” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Metendothenia separatana (Kearfott, 1907). “Waq., Aug. 1, 1936; Wyer’s Valley, Aug. 20, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Hedia separatana* Kft.).

Notocelia culminana (Walsingham, 1879). “Well distributed but infrequent, Aug. 27–Sept. 8” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Epiblema culminana* Wlshm.).

Notocelia rosaecolana (Doubleday, 1850). According to Jason Dombroskie, this is the likely identity of the species listed by Johnson (1930) as *Eucosma suffusana* Zell., “June 24. Larva in

the flower buds and young leaves of the young roses.” This species was listed by Jones & Kimball (1943) as *Epiblema suffusana* Zell.: “Waq., July 5, 1939; Town, June 30 and July 6, 1941 (Miss Wyatt).”

Olethreutes spp. “Of this difficult genus, the presence of several additional species, including at least one undescribed, is indicated by captures made on one or both islands [Nantucket & Martha’s Vineyard]” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema* Clem.).

Olethreutes appendiceum (Zeller, 1875). “Polpis. July 9, 1940; July 12, 1941; Waq., July 6, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema appendiceum* Zell.).

Olethreutes astrologana (Zeller, 1875). “Well distributed but infrequent. June 19–July 17” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Olethreutes bipartitana (Clemens, 1860). “Hummock Pond, July 21” (Johnson 1930); “Common. June 23–July 24” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Olethreutes concinnana (Clemens, 1865). “Maxcys Pond, July 21. Polpis, July 27. Larva feeds on blackberry” (Johnson 1930, *Cymolomia concinnana* Clem.). (Listed as *Exartema concinnum* Clem. by Jones & Kimball 1943; no additional records.)

Olethreutes coruscana (Clemens, 1860). “Polpis and Waq., rare. July 3 to 9” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *O. constellatana* Zell.).

Olethreutes ?diallacta (Meyrick, 1932). “Waq. and swamp areas, rare. July 16–23” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema ?trepidulum* Heinr.).

Olethreutes fasciatana (Clemens, 1860). “Polpis, and Waq., rare. July 5–23” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema fasciatanum* Clem.).

Olethreutes glaciana (Möschler, 1860). “Maxcys Pond, July 21–24” (Johnson 1930, *O. fuscibana* Zell.); “Among numerous examples of *bipartitana*, a single specimen of *glaciana* was detected and its identity confirmed by dissection, U.S.N.M., 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Olethreutes melanomesum (Heinrich, 1923). “Moderately common. July 9–29” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema melanomesum* Heinr.).

Olethreutes ?merrickanum (Kearfott, 1907). “Waq., July 21, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema ?merrickanum* Kft.).

Olethreutes olivaceana (Fernald, 1882). “Maxcys Pond, July 21. Taupaushaw, Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Cymolomia olivaceana* Fern.); “Common. July 5–Aug. 17” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema olivaceanum* Fern.).

Olethreutes permundana (Clemens, 1860). “Waq., rare. July 16–27” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema permundanum* Clem.).

Olethreutes sericoranum (Walsingham, 1879). “Waq., Aug. 16, 1941 (2)” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema sericoranum* Wlsh.). An adult resembling this species was reared from a leaf-tying larva on huckleberry, Head of the Plains, 6/10/2016, adult 7/12/2016 (BG 1311988; CUIC).

Olethreutes nr. subnubilum (Heinrich, 1923). “Pine woods, July 29, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exartema nr. subnubilum* Heinr.).

Orthotaenia undulana (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). “Waq., June 20, 1942” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Badebecia urticana* Hbn.).

Pandemis limitata (Robinson, 1869). “Waq., July 31 and Aug. 15, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Pelochrista agricolana (Walsingham, 1879). “Common, June 4–Aug. 11” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Eucosma pergandeana* Fern.).

Pelochrista albiguttana (Zeller, 1875). “Polpis, July 12, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Eucosma albiguttana* Zell.).

Pelochrista cataclystiana (Walker, 1863). “Common. July 6–Oct. 6” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Eucosma cataclystiana* Wlk.).

Pelochrista derelicta (Heinrich, 1929). “Swamp area, July 22, 1941 (2); sea shore, July 27, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Eucosma derelicta* Heinr.).

Pelochrista dorsisignatana (Clemens, 1860). Reared from roots of seaside goldenrod. “Waq., infrequent” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Eucosma dorsisignatana* Clem.).

Pelochrista lathamii (Forbes, 1937). “Numerous in 1936, otherwise infrequent. July 3–Aug. 3” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Eucosma lathamii* Forbes).

Pelochrista ridingsana (Robinson, 1869). “Forbes (Lepid. N. Y., p. 423) says ‘A dwarf variant of this form also occurs in Nantucket, Massachusetts’” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Eucosma ridingsana* Rob.).

Pelochrista zomonana (Kearfott, 1907). “Maxcys Pond, June 21” (Johnson 1930, *Eucosma zomonana* Kf.); “Waq., June 21, 1928 (CWJ); Polpis, May 24 and July 10, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *E. zomonana* Kft.).

Phaecasiophora confixana (Walker, 1863). “Polpis, and Town, infrequent. May 24–July 29” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

* *Phaecasiophora niveiguttana* Grote, 1873. Labyrinth moth. Reared from a larva tying sassafras leaves, Masquetuck, 7/28/2017, adult ~9/1/2017 (BG 1462660; CSE).

Phtheochroa baracana (Busck, 1907). “Fairly common. July 13–Sept. 20” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Hysterosia baracana* Busck).

Phtheochroa nr. birdana (Busck, 1907). “Waq., July 13, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Hysterosia nr. birdana* Busck).

Phtheochroa cartwrightana (Kearfott, 1907). “Waq., Aug. 5, 1936 (2); Polpis, July 9, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Hysterosia cartwrightana* Kft.).

Platynota idaeusalis (Walker, 1859). “Polpis, locally common. June 10–July 11” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Platynota flavedana Clemens, 1860. Reared from a larva tying leaves of *Crocantemum*, Head of the Plains, 6/10/2016, adult 7/1/2016 (BG 1309869; CSE); “Taupaushaw, July 25, 1928” (Johnson 1930, *Sparganothis flavedana* Clem.); “Common. June 19–July 31” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Proteoteras aesculana (Riley, 1881). “In A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

* *Pseudexentera maracana* (Kearfott, 1907). Reared from bayberry, Ice Pond Lot (CNC; BG 870705).

Pseudexentera nr. spoliata (Clemens, 1864). “Well distributed but rare. May 12–June 20” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exentera nr. spoliata* Clem.).

Pseudogalleria inimicella (Zeller, 1872). “Polpis, July 2, 1936; July 9, 1940” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Retinia comstockiana (Fernald, 1879). Bores in twigs of pitch pine. “Well distributed but rare. June 19–July 22” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Petrova comstockiana* Fern.).

Retinia virginiana (Busck, 1914). “Not uncommon. July 6–Aug. 9” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Petrova virginiana* Busck).

Rhopobota dietziana (Kearfott, 1907). Leaf mines on winterberry, Coskata Woods, 9/9/2011; at Tuckernuck, 9/10/2011; “Waq., infrequent. May 21–July 6” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Norma dietziana* Kft.).

Rhopobota finitimana (Heinrich, 1923). Larvae tie leaves of winterberry. “Polpis, July 12, 1941” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Kundrya finitimana* Heinr.).

Rhopobota naevana (Hübner, 1814). Black-headed fireworm moth. “Reported from the cranberry bogs” (Johnson 1930); “also in A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Rhyacionia frustrana (Scudder, in Comstock, 1880). Nantucket pine tip moth. “The larva of this moth infests the new growth of the [pitch] pine. It destroyed a large area of the pines in 1927, but its destructive work was scarcely noticeable in 1929” (Johnson 1930); “See Scudder’s paper, ‘The Pine Moth of Nantucket’ (Pub. Mass. Soc. for the Promotion of Agric., 1883)” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Rhyacionia rigidana (Fernald, 1880). “Pine woods, Apr. 20, 1936” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Sereda tautana (Clemens, 1865). “Scrub oak area, May 6 and 16, 1941; Waq., Apr. 18, 1942” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *S. lautana* Clem.).

Sonia constrictana (Zeller, 1875). “Fairly common. July 5–Aug. 16” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Sparganothis lycopodiana (Kearfott, 1907). “Waq., and sea shore, rare. June 30–Sept. 20” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Sparganothis sulfureana (Clemens, 1860). “Maxcys Pond, July 16–26. The larva feeds on grape, willow, etc.” (Johnson 1930); “Fairly common. June 30–Sept. 20” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Sparganothis unifasciana (Clemens, 1864). “Not rare. June 30–July 29” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Sparganothis xanthoides (Walker, 1863). “Polpis, and Waq., infrequent. June 16–July 16” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Spilonota ocellana (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775). Eye-spotted bud moth. “In A. Bolter coll.” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Strepsicrates smithiana (Walsingham, 1891). Bayberry leaf-tier moth. Larvae on bayberry, Linda Loring Nature Foundation, 7/27/2017, adult 8/18–19/2017 (BG 1462645; CSE); “Waq., July 6, 1940; June 26, 1942” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *S. smithiana* Wlsh, var. *indentana* Dyar).

Syndemis afflictana (Walker, 1863). At light, UMass field station, 5/19/2012 (BG 734059); “Very common. May 8–July 21” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Tortrix afflictana* Wlk.).

Taniva albolineana (Kearfott, 1907). Spruce needle-miner moth. “Town, June 30 and July 29, 1941 (Miss Harwood)” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

Thyralia bunteana (Robinson, 1869). “Waq., Sept. 6, 1937” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Phalonia bunteana* Rob.).

Xenotemna pallorana (Robinson, 1869). “Well distributed but infrequent. June 15–Sept. 7” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Tortrix pallorana* Rob.).

Zeiraphera improbana (Walker, 1863). “Common. Apr. 23–June 20” (Jones & Kimball 1943, *Exentera improbana* Wlk.).

Zomaria interruptolineana (Fernald, 1882). At light, 8/12/2012 (BG 741541); State Forest, 6/10/2013 (BG 858246); reared from larva tying leaves of *Vaccinium angustifolium*, Dead Horse Valley, 7/26/2017, adults 8/20–23/2017 (BG 1462646, BG 1462648; CSE); larvae on *Gaylussacia frondosa*, Masquetuck, 7/28/2017, adult 8/15/2017 (BG 1462641; CSE); “Common. May 24–June 8. . . The larvae web together the leaves of huckleberry, and pupate between the leaves; adults emerge late July, Aug.” (Jones & Kimball 1943).

DIPTERA (Flies)

TEPHRITOIDEA

(Johnson 1930, pp. 150–151)

LONCHAEIDAE (Lance Flies)

Earomyia aterrima (Malloch, 1920). “Fair grounds, June 9 and 23. Miacomet Pond, June 24” (Johnson 1930, *Lonchaea aterrima* Mall.).

Lonchaea polita Say, 1830. “Taupaushaw, Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930).

PLATYSTOMATIDAE (Signal Flies)

Rivellia boscii Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830. “Hummock Pond, June 21. July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930).

Rivellia brevifasciata Johnson, 1900. “On goat’s rue (*Tephrosia virginiana*). Surfside and woods near Hummock Pond, June 21–Aug. 9. Tuckernuck, July 21 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930).

Rivellia conjuncta Loew, 1873. “June 23–July 25” (Johnson 1930).

Rivellia quadrifasciata (Macquart, 1835). “July 11 (Morse)” (Johnson 1930).

TEPHRITIDAE (Fruit Flies)

Acinia picturata (Snow, 1894). Larvae feed on *Pluchea* seeds. “Tuckernuck, Aug. 6, 1909 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930, *Tephritis fucata* Fab.).

Campiglossa albiceps (Loew, 1873). Larvae feed in flower heads of asters. “June 23–Sept. 14” (Johnson 1930, *Tephritis albiceps* Loew).

Euaestoides abstersus (Loew, 1862). “Surfside, Sept. 12–16” (Johnson 1930, *Trypanea abstersa* Loew).

Eurosta solidaginis (Fitch, 1855). Forms spherical galls on goldenrod stems. “Aug. 26 (Sanford)” (Johnson 1930, *E. asteri* Harr.).

Neaspilota achilleae Johnson, 1900. Larvae feed on various Asteraceae. “June 2 (Brooks). June 8–Sept. 8. Frequents the flower buds of yarrow (*Achillea millefolium*)” (Johnson 1930).

Procecidochares polita (Loew, 1862). Forms rosette galls on goldenrod. “Taupaushaw, Aug. 17 and Sept. 9” (Johnson 1930). Gall of this species or *P. atra* (Loew, 1862) found on *Solidago rugosa* at NCF Bird Sanctuary, 8/7/2012.

* *Rhagoletis cingulata* (Loew, 1862). Larvae feed in fruits of black cherry and other *Prunus* spp. Photographed by Bo Zaremba at moth sheet, 8/6/2012 (BG 688049).

Tephritis pura (Loew, 1873). On goldenrods. “July 4, 1905 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930, *Euaresta pura* Loew).

Terellia palposa (Loew, 1862). “June 24–Aug. 9. The larva lives in the flower buds of the pasture thistle (*Cirsium pumilum*)” (Johnson 1930). Nectaring on oxeye daisy, Russell's Way, 6/10/2013 (BG 858222); congregating on *Cirsium horridulum*, Head of the Plains, 6/10/2016 (BG 1302557; CSE).

Trupanea dacetoptera (Phillips, 1923). Hosts include *Heterotheca* and *Pseudognaphalium*. “June 23–Sept. 13. Tuckernuck, Aug. 6 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930).

Zonosemata electa (Say, 1830). Pepper Maggot. Larvae feed in fruits of tomato, pepper, and eggplant. “Taupaushaw, July 25 and Aug. 17” (Johnson 1930, *Zonosema flavonotata* Macq.).

ULIDIIDAE (Picture-winged Flies)

Chaetopsis aenea (Wiedemann, 1830). “Common in salt and brackish marshes, June 25–Aug. 21. Muskeget, July 11 (Brooks)” (Johnson 1930).

Chaetopsis apicalis Johnson, 1900. “Common in salt and brackish marshes, June 9–Aug. 21. Muskeget, July 11 (Brooks)” (Johnson 1930).

Chaetopsis fulvifrons (Macquart, 1855). “June 1–Sept. 10” (Johnson 1930). At black light, 8/5/2012 (BG 688051).

Chaetopsis massyla (Walker, 1849). “In fresh water marshes, June 25–Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930). Grove Lane, south of No Bottom Pond, 7/31/2017 (BG 1462181).

Delphinia picta (Fabricius, 1781). “June 21–July 16” (Johnson 1930, *Camptoneura picta* Fab.).

Euxesta notata (Wiedemann, 1830). “Grove Lane, June 21” (Johnson 1930).

Physiphora nasoni Cresson, 1913. “July 3. July 11 (Morse). Tuckernuck, Aug. 6 (Cushman)” (Johnson 1930, *Stenomyia nasoni* Cress.).

Physiphora tenuis Loew, 1868. “July 4 (Cushman). Surfside, Aug. 8” (Johnson 1930, *Stenomyia tenuis* Loew).

Seioptera vibrans (Linnaeus, 1758). “Grove Lane, June 21” (Johnson 1930).

Stenomyia scoriacea (Loew, 1876). “Madaket, June 16” (Johnson 1930, *Euxesta scoriacea* Loew).

LITERATURE CITED

- Bright, D. E. 1994. Revision of the genus *Sitona* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) of North America. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America* 87(3):277–306.
- Eiseman, C. S. 2015a. Notes on leaf-mining Chrysomelidae (Coleoptera) in New England. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 69(3):453–458.
- Eiseman, C. S. 2015b. On the distinctive feeding pattern of *Sterictiphora* Billberg (Hymenoptera: Argidae) sawfly larvae. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington* 117(1):65–67.
- Eiseman, Charles S., Donald R. Davis, Julia A. Blyth, David L. Wagner, Michael W. Palmer, and Tracy S. Feldman. 2017. A new species of *Marmara* (Lepidoptera: Gracillariidae: Marmarinae), with an annotated list of known hostplants for the genus. *Zootaxa* 4337(2):198–222.
- Eiseman, C. S. and A. S. Jensen. 2015. Insects feeding on sea lavender (Plumbaginaceae: *Limonium carolinianum* [Walt.] Britt) along the New England coast. *Entomological News* 124(5):364–369.
- Eiseman, Charles S. and David R. Smith. 2017. Nearctic Species of *Metallus* Forbes (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae): Biology and Distribution. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington* 119(4):551–564.
- Gibson, Gary A. P. 2011. The species of *Eupelmus* (*Eupelmus*) Dalman and *Eupelmus* (*Episolidelia*) Girault (Hymenoptera: Eupelmidae) in North America north of Mexico. *Zootaxa* 2951:1–97.
- Hespenheide, H. A. and C. S. Eiseman. 2016. A new species of *Brachys* Dejean, 1833 (Coleoptera: Buprestidae) from the eastern United States using an unusual host. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 70(2):335–340.
- Johnson, C. W. 1928. The New England Siricidae or Horntails. *Bulletin of the Boston Society of Natural History* 49(Oct.):3–7.
- Johnson, C. W. 1930. A List of the Insect Fauna of Nantucket, Massachusetts. *Publications of the Nantucket Maria Mitchell Association Vol III, No. 2.*
- Jones, Frank Morton and Charles P. Kimball. 1943. The Lepidoptera of Nantucket and Marthas Vineyard Islands, Massachusetts. *Publications of the Nantucket Maria Mitchell Association Vol IV.*
- Kingsolver, J. M. 2004. Handbook of the Bruchidae of the United States and Canada (Insecta, Coleoptera). United States Department of Agriculture Agricultural Research Service Technical Bulletin Number 1912, Volume 1.

- Smith, D. R. 1971. Nearctic Sawflies III. Heterarthrinae: Adults and Larvae (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae). U.S. Department of Agriculture Agricultural Research Service Technical Bulletin No. 1420.
- Smith, D. R. 1989. The sawfly genus *Arge* (Hymenoptera: Argidae) in the Western Hemisphere. Transactions of the American Entomological Society 115(2):83–205.
- Smith, E. H. 1985. Revision of the genus *Phyllostreta* Chevrolat of America north of Mexico. Part I. The maculate species (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae, Alticinae). Fieldiana, Zoology (new series) 28:1–168.